

**GUIDANCE FOR
COALITIONS INFORMING
THE STANDARDISATION
AND IMPLEMENTATION OF
PSYCHEDELIC THERAPIES
IN EUROPE**

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Colophon

Guidance for Coalitions informing the Standardisation and Implementation of Psychedelic Therapies in Europe

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Abstract

Mental health has become a priority for the European Union (EU), with increasing recognition of the limitations of current therapeutic treatments and the need for novel approaches. Classical and atypical psychedelics are increasingly considered as promising interventions for the treatment of several mental health conditions and to support patients in palliative care. At the same time, there is also an increase in policy and commercial interest, as well as early medical access and non-medical use cases. The PsyPal project is the first EU-funded, multi-site clinical trial investigating psilocybin-assisted therapy for alleviating existential distress in individuals living with life-limiting illnesses, including Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD), Multiple Sclerosis (MS), Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS), and Atypical Parkinson's Disease (APD). This guidance paper builds on the experiences gained in scientific research, therapist training, and public engagement to provide a picture of the current stakeholder environment for psychedelic therapies in Europe. The paper draws on a stakeholder consultation involving perspectives from across scientific research, clinical practice, patient experience, regulatory agencies, industry, media, and civil society. The paper considers the perspectives and priorities of actors from across the space to identify knowledge and cooperation gaps. This is used to develop a set of recommendations to advise the formation and sustainment of coalitions and initiatives across sectors that aim to inform the standardisation and potential implementation of psychedelic therapies in the EU.

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Abbreviations

ADEPT	Advanced Education in Psychedelic Therapy
AEMPS	Spanish Agency of Medicines and Medical Devices
ALS	Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis
APD	Atypical Parkinson's Disease
APT	Augmented Psychotherapy Training
BfArM	Federal Institute for Drugs and Medical Devices
CIMH	Central Institute of Mental Health (Mannheim)
COPD	Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease
CNECV	National Council of Ethics for Life Sciences (Portugal)
CZEPS	Czech Psychedelics Society
DMT	Dimethyltryptamine
EAN	European Academy of Neurology
EAPC	European Association for Palliative Care
EBC	European Brain Council
EC	European Commission
ECI	European Citizens Initiative
ECNP	European College of Neuropsychopharmacology
EFNA	European Federation of Neurological Associations
EFPA	European Federation of Psychologists' Associations
EFPIA	European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EP	European Parliament
EPA	European Psychiatric Association
EPACA	European Public Affairs Consultancies Association
EPIsoDE	Efficacy and Safety of Psilocybin in Treatment-Resistant Major Depression
EU	European Union
EUFAMI	European Federation of Associations of Families of People with Mental Illness
EUTR	European Union Transparency Register
FENS	Federation of European Neuroscience Societies
FDA	Food and Drug Administration (United States)
G-BA	Federal Joint Committee (Germany)
GAMIAN-Europe	Global Alliance of Mental Illness Advocacy Networks Europe
ICPR	Interdisciplinary Conference on Psychedelic Research
INFRAMED	Authority for Medication (Portugal)
LSD	Lysergic Acid Diethylamide
MAPS	Multidisciplinary Association for Psychedelic Studies
MDD	Major Depressive Disorder
MDMA	Methylenedioxymethamphetamine
MEP	Member of the European Parliament
MS	Multiple Sclerosis
NM	Norrskén Mind
NWvP	Netherlands Psychiatric Association
OF	Pharmacists Association (Portugal)
OM	Medical Association (Portugal)

OPP	Portuguese Psychologists Association
PAREA	Psychedelic Access and Research European Alliance
PARS	Psychedelics and Related Substances
PsyPal	Psilocybin Therapy for Psychological Distress in Palliative Care Patients
PsyPAN	Participant Advocacy Network
PTSD	Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder
ReSPCT	Reporting of Setting in Psychedelic Clinical Trials
REMS	Risk Evaluation and Mitigation Strategy
RMP	Risk Management Plan
SNRI	Serotonin-Norepinephrine Reuptake Inhibitors
SSRI	Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitors
SUD	Substance Use Disorder
SÚKL	Institute for Drug Control (Czechia)
TGA	Therapeutic Goods Administration
TRD	Treatment-Resistant Depression
VZP	General Health Insurance Company (Czechia)
UK	United Kingdom
UN	United Nations
US	United States
ZiN	National Health Care Institute (Netherlands)

1. Introduction

The European Union (EU) increasingly recognises mental health as a public health priority.¹ Mental health conditions are associated with significant personal, economic, and societal burdens. At the same time, there is concern that the pace of therapeutic innovation in psychiatry and the scale of investment into care services remains insufficient to address the apparent mental health crisis. In this context, there is a renewed interest in the therapeutic potential of psychedelic therapies, supported by the promising evidence of their effectiveness and safety.² Psychedelics are therefore increasingly considered as a novel and promising approach to addressing conditions where current pharmacological treatments are showing limitations, including in cases of treatment-resistant depression (TRD), generalised anxiety disorder (GAD), post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), substance use disorder (SUD), and existential distress in persons with life-limiting conditions.³ As part of these developments, the PsyPal project became the first multi-site clinical study into psychedelic therapy to receive EU research and innovation funds. This guidance paper is the result of a commitment by the PsyPal consortium to provide guidance to a stakeholder environment across scientific research, clinical practice, patient experience, regulatory agencies, industry, and civil society. The paper shares perspectives, questions, concerns, and priorities from these communities with the aim to identify knowledge and cooperation gaps. The paper then develops a set of 10 recommendations to advise the formation and sustainment of coalitions and initiatives across sectors that aim to inform the standardisation and potential implementation of psychedelic therapies in the EU.

1.1 Introduction to the Project

PsyPal investigates the potential of psilocybin therapy to alleviate existential distress in people living with life-limiting conditions requiring palliative care, including conditions such as Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD), Multiple Sclerosis (MS), Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS), and Atypical Parkinson's Disease (APD). The project's multi-site clinical trial builds on earlier clinical studies showing promising effects of psychedelic therapy on mood, anxiety, and quality of life for patients. The project adopts a comprehensive perspective that assists patients, caregivers, healthcare professionals, and public institutions with the knowledge to make informed, empirically supported decisions about palliative care. PsyPal aims therefore to contribute to the reduction of healthcare, economic, and societal burden of increasing palliative care needs and ensure that persons suffering with existential distress are better supported to address their spiritual, emotional, and psychological needs.

1.2 Aims of the Paper

As an answer to these questions raised beyond its clinical study, the project also focuses on identifying barriers to the implementation of psychedelic therapies and proposing strategies to

¹ European Commission (2023). *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on a Comprehensive Approach to Mental Health*. European Commission. COM(2023) 298.

² Destoop M, Mohr P, Butlen-Ducuing F, Kéri P, Samochowiec J, De Picker L, Fiorillo A, Kuypers KPC, Dom G (2025). *Use of psychedelic treatments in psychiatric clinical practice: an EPA policy paper*. *European Psychiatry*, 68(1), 1–7.

³ European Medicines Agency (2024). *EMA Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics: Workshop Report*.

building collaboration and consensus to overcome them. This guidance paper contributes to that overall commitment by investigating the stakeholder environment for psychedelic therapies. Its principal aim is to provide an understanding of and recommendations for practicable steps towards the establishment of sustainable multi-stakeholder coalitions and the standardisation of psychedelic therapies in the EU. The guidance paper adopts a research-informed method to developing these recommendations and approaches the rationale for and pathways towards standardisation and coalitions as open questions.

1.3 Scope of the Paper

This guidance paper addresses the broader stakeholder environment for psychedelic therapies in the EU. This includes perspectives from patient and participant experience, informal and voluntary care, spiritual and psychosocial care, clinical care, scientific research, healthcare professions, healthcare systems, health technology assessment, regulatory agencies, legislative institutions, pharmaceutical industry, education, training, journalism, communication, advocacy, consultancies, and civil society organisations. The input and takeaways are informed by research from across scientific and medical fields, including psychiatry, psychology, pharmacology, neurology, economics, law, policy, culture, and ethics.

Classical and Atypical Psychedelics

The term *psychedelic*, from the Greek *psychē* (soul, mind) and *dēlein* (to reveal, to manifest), can be applied to a range of compounds with different pharmacological and subjective effects.⁴ In the context of investigations into their potential for treating mental health conditions, these are generally categorised as either classical or atypical psychedelics.⁵ This paper primarily addresses the standardisation and integration of therapies involving *classical psychedelics*, including psilocybin (and psilocin), lysergic acid diethylamide (LSD), and dimethyltryptamine (DMT). The paper also considers some *atypical psychedelics*, such as the dissociative anaesthetics, ketamine and esketamine and the entactogen, methylenedioxymethamphetamine (MDMA). Classical psychedelics act on the serotonergic system, producing effects that impact mood, perception, and cognition. Atypical psychedelics overlap with classical psychedelics in certain psychoactive effects, though they act through distinct though understudied pharmacological mechanisms. Classical psychedelics are also not uniform, they can act on monoamine transporters, dopamine receptors, adrenergic receptors to differing degrees and produce different phenomenological effects.⁶

Psychedelics Renaissance

Psychedelics have a history of spiritual use among certain indigenous peoples, such as in the use of psilocybin mushrooms and ayahuasca preparations in the Americas.⁷ Scientific research into the therapeutic potential of psychedelics started to increase in the 1950s. The classification of

⁴ Royal College of Psychiatrists (2025) College Position Statement PS02/25: [Psychedelic and related substances \(PARS\) for medical use \(including pharmacologically assisted psychotherapy\)](#).

⁵ European Medicines Agency (2024). [EMA Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics: Workshop Report](#).

⁶ Ramaekers JG, Mallaroni P, Mason NL, Avram M (2018). [Not all psychedelics are created equal](#). *Nature Mental Health*, 3(12), 1465–1467.

⁷ Rucker JJH, Iliff J, Nutt D (2018). [Psychiatry & the Psychedelic Drugs. Past, Present & Future](#). *Neuropharmacology*, 142, 200–218.

psychedelics as scheduled substances with the 1971 United Nations Convention on Psychotropic Substances significantly restricted the continuation of psychedelic research.⁸ This guidance paper will consider the period of renewed scientific and clinical interest in psychedelics, starting in the 1990s and accelerating in the 2010s. This period is sometimes referred to as the *psychedelics renaissance*. It is important to acknowledge that this is an evolving field of science and practice. This paper reflects the state of knowledge and developments until December 2025.

Standardisation and Coalitions

This guidance paper focuses on the interconnected priorities of developing standards and building coalitions across the relevant stakeholder groups in the EU. It addresses the need for standardisation in care, training, science, regulation, and implementation; recognising that comprehensive protocols and guidelines are important contributors to evidence-based practices that ensure patient safety and equitable access. It also considers the potential formation of sustainable and effective stakeholder coalitions; ranging from formal legal entities to advisory groups and dialogue platforms that support knowledge sharing and policy alignment across sectors.

1.4 Research Approach

This guidance paper was completed in December 2025. The research phase started in January 2025. This followed a significant increase in consensus and coalition-building initiatives in the psychedelics space in Europe. These include the European Medicines Agency (EMA) Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics in April 2024,⁹ the legal incorporation of the Psychedelic Access and Research European Alliance (PAREA) in December 2024, the publication of the European Psychiatric Association (EPA) Policy Paper on Psychedelic Use in Psychiatry in January 2025.¹⁰ The paper aims to provide an answer to a primary research question, *what pathways exist for psychedelic therapies to be standardised and sustainably implemented across the EU?* The paper then considers the additional research questions, *what role can multi-stakeholder coalitions have in informing this process and what factors shape the effectiveness and sustainability of such multi-stakeholder coalitions?*

Stakeholder Consultation

The research phase for the paper was informed by a consultation process, including 21 semi-structured interviews with stakeholders conducted between July and September 2025. The interviews followed a common guide to ensure comparability, while allowing adaptation to each participants' areas of expertise and countries of activity. Interview contacts were selected through a nomination process carried out by a group of PsyPal partners to minimise imbalance, ensure diversity, and arrive at a consensus. Interview participants were mapped against 12 stakeholder categories to track the representativeness of the consultation and understand the overlaps in

⁸ United Nations Economic and Social Council (1971). *Final Act of the United Nations Conference for the Adoption of a Protocol on Psychotropic Substances*.

⁹ European Medicines Agency (2024). *EMA Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics: Workshop Report*.

¹⁰ Destoop M, Mohr P, Butlen-Ducuing F, Kéri P, Samochowiec J, De Picker L, Fiorillo A, Kuypers KPC, Dom G (2025). *Use of psychedelic treatments in psychiatric clinical practice: an EPA policy paper*. *European Psychiatry*, 68(1), 1–7.

perspectives, given that some interviewees were active in multiple capacities, sectors, and settings.

1.5 Structure of the Paper

The guidance paper is organised into nine sections. Section 2 provides a narrative review of scientific and clinical research on psychedelic therapies, the current evidence, methodological challenges relating to expectancy and unblinding, and persistent questions relating the role of psychotherapy, as well as researcher priorities. Section 3 presents some of the cases and experiences of psychedelic therapies in clinical and non-medical care, with a focus on practical and ethical considerations, such as patient safety, informed consent, and equitable access. Section 4 presents recent EU and national regulatory developments and perspectives shaping the implementation and integration into healthcare systems. Section 5 considers the available pathways towards access, implementation, and commercialisation. Section 6 shares perspectives from the diverse civil society environment and experiences in advocacy, public communication, community engagement, and the development of guidance. Section 7 shares insights from on forming and sustaining multi-stakeholder coalitions and initiatives, from their purpose, functions, governance, funding, and resources. Section 8 presents a set of recommendations for stakeholders aiming to inform the standardisation and potential implementation of psychedelic therapies. Section 9 reflects on the recent pace of change in the psychedelic space and proposes directions for future initiatives in Europe.

2. Scientific and Clinical Research

Scientific and clinical research on psychedelic therapies has expanded rapidly, signalling renewed interest in their therapeutic potential. Neuroimaging and psychopharmacology studies indicate the safe use of psychedelic compounds.¹¹ Clinical trials continued to provide promising indications of efficacy and safety for the treatment of several mental health conditions. Psychedelic compounds however represent distinctive methodological challenges for clinical research, such as expectancy and blinding effects, and translational questions, such as the role of the psychotherapeutic component. Researchers have also identified knowledge gaps and defined research priorities that address understudied areas that are significant for future potential implementation, such as standardised protocols, patient experiences, concomitant medication use, and health economics. Although a comprehensive overview of current research in the field is beyond the scope of this paper, this section concentrates on the scientific and clinical themes most relevant to the broader conversation on the standardisation and implementation of psychedelic therapies.

2.1 Current Evidence

Classical and atypical psychedelics are investigated for their potential to treat a range of mental health conditions, including TRD, GAD, PTSD, and existential distress and anxiety in palliative care for life-limiting conditions.¹² Clinical trials have reported encouraging, though still preliminary, findings across these indications. Psilocybin, a classical psychedelic, has demonstrated variable but generally positive outcomes in open-label and placebo-controlled studies targeting depression, anxiety, and addiction when combined with psychotherapy in controlled clinical environments.¹³ Ketamine, an atypical psychedelic, has the most extensive clinical evidence base, due to its long-standing use as an anaesthetic at higher doses and the current registration of esketamine for the treatment of TRD.¹⁴ Psychedelic treatment is overall a diverse and fast evolving field in mental health research. The Royal College of Psychiatrists position paper provides a detailed discussion of the evidence base for each of the most common psychedelic compounds, relevant to clinicians, with information on efficacy, safety, and mechanisms of action.¹⁵

Clinical research has also explored the use of psychedelics for indications aside from TRD, PTSD, and existential distress, with several systematic reviews examining their therapeutic potential. Research has also shown their safety and efficacy for major depressive disorder (MDD).¹⁶ Recent analyses indicate that psilocybin shows promising efficacy in the treatment of substance use

¹¹ Royal College of Psychiatrists (2025) College Position Statement PS02/25: [Psychedelic and related substances \(PARS\) for medical use \(including pharmacologically assisted psychotherapy\)](#).

¹² Luoma JB, Chwyl C, Bathje GJ, David AK, Lancelotta R (2000). [A Meta-Analysis of Placebo-Controlled Trials of Psychedelic-Assisted Therapy](#). *Journal of Psychoactive Drugs*, 52(4), 289–299.

¹³ Andrade FRT, Buchborn T, Thalheimer G, Meinhardt MW, Joca S, de Almeida RMM. [Therapeutic Use of Psilocybin in Depression: A Systematic Review of Clinical Evidence](#). *Acta Neuropsychiatrica*, 37, e86.

¹⁴ Schenberg EE (2018) [Psychedelic-Assisted Psychotherapy: A Paradigm Shift in Psychiatric Research and Development](#). *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 9(733).

¹⁵ Royal College of Psychiatrists (2025) College Position Statement PS02/25: [Psychedelic and related substances \(PARS\) for medical use \(including pharmacologically assisted psychotherapy\)](#).

¹⁶ Świeczkowski D, Kwaśny A, Pruc M, Gaca Z, Lukasz S, Wiesław JC (2024). [Efficacy and safety of psilocybin in the treatment of Major Depressive Disorder \(MDD\): A dose-response network meta-analysis of randomized placebo-controlled clinical trials](#). *Psychiatry Research*, 344.

disorders (SUD), particularly alcohol and nicotine dependence.¹⁷ A review suggests that psilocybin may alleviate symptoms of obsessive–compulsive disorder (OCD).¹⁸ Another systematic review of clinical trials reported reductions in suicidality following psychedelic therapy.¹⁹ Authors often note that these findings remain preliminary and recommend additional dedicated research on the potential of psychedelics for the treatment of these conditions.

The increased interest in psychedelic research and the promising results emerging from early trials have prompted some researchers to question whether this development represents a paradigm shift in mental health care.²⁰ Psychedelics provide novel features, therapeutic effects, and mechanisms of action compared to treatments currently available. Another perspective proposes that this resurgence may be better understood as an integration of psychedelics into current bio-psycho-social models of mental health, with psychedelics acting as amplifiers of established psychological processes.²¹ The importance of psychotherapy and the need to adapt healthcare infrastructures to accommodate these treatment models has also been emphasised.²² The EPA policy paper has cautioned clinicians against accepting optimistic positions without sufficient scientific support, under the influence of public, media, and commercial enthusiasm.²³ The EMA and professional associations, meanwhile, continue to emphasise the need to address persistent methodological challenges in psychedelic clinical research before these treatments can be fully integrated into healthcare practice.²⁴

2.2 Methodological Challenges

Among the methodological challenges in clinical research identified across sectors, blinding and expectancy remain the most persistent. Questions relating to the psychosocial aspects of psychedelic therapy are also frequently raised, particularly by regulators. At the same time, these questions have become the focus of a broader academic discussion about the nature of therapeutic mechanisms in psychedelic interventions. Researchers have also identified additional priorities for the field. A report on reimbursement pathways, funded by Norrskén Mind, a foundation focused on supporting research on psychedelic substances and their potential as treatments for mental health disorders, provides a more detailed discussion of the challenges in

¹⁷ Mertens LJ, Preller KH (2021). *Classical Psychedelics as Therapeutics in Psychiatry - Current Clinical Evidence and Potential Therapeutic Mechanisms in Substance Use and Mood Disorders*. *Pharmacopsychiatry*, 54(4), 176-190.

¹⁸ Collins HM (2024). *Psychedelics for the Treatment of Obsessive–Compulsive Disorder: Efficacy and Proposed Mechanisms*. *International Journal of Neuropsychopharmacology*, 27(12).

¹⁹ Zeifman R, Yu D, Singhal N, Wang G, Nayak SM, Weissman CR (2022). *Decreases in Suicidality Following Psychedelic Therapy: A Meta-Analysis of Individual Patient Data Across Clinical Trials*. *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 83(2).

²⁰ Schenberg EE (2018). *Psychedelic-Assisted Psychotherapy: A Paradigm Shift in Psychiatric Research and Development*. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 9(733).

²¹ Aicher HD, Wolff M, Herwig U (2024). *Psychedelic therapy – refining the claim of a paradigm shift*. *International Review of Psychiatry*, 36(8), 920–927.

²² Gründer G (2021). *Psychedelics: A New Treatment Paradigm in Psychiatry?*. *Pharmacopsychiatry*, 54(4) 149-150.

²³ Destoop M, Mohr P, Butlen-Ducuing F, Kéri P, Samochowiec J, De Picker L, Fiorillo A, Kuypers KPC, Dom G (2025). *Use of psychedelic treatments in psychiatric clinical practice: an EPA policy paper*. *European Psychiatry*, 68(1), 1–7.

²⁴ European Medicines Agency (2024). *EMA Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics: Workshop Report*.

designing clinical trials for psychedelic therapies and the implications for their regulation and implementation into clinical care.²⁵

Expectancy Effects

The effects of patient expectations present a significant methodological challenge in psychedelic research. Positive expectancy can lead individuals to overestimate the therapeutic potential of the intervention, thereby amplifying perceived treatment effects. Negative expectancy may result in symptom exacerbation when participants feel disappointed at receiving a placebo instead of the active compound, a nocebo effect, or when they do not experience the expected therapeutic response after taking the active treatment. With the growing public perception of psychedelics as promising pharmacological tools for mental health conditions, it is reasonable to assume that positive expectancy is becoming increasingly prevalent among potential study participants. For instance, in a trial comparing psilocybin to escitalopram, self-referred participants frequently expressed a preference for psilocybin, creating a risk that disappointment among those who believed they had received escitalopram could influence outcome comparisons. Researchers have therefore implemented strategies to mitigate expectancy effects. These include improvements in patient screening, qualitative surveys, informed consent, facilitator training and trial designs. One such option is to offer participants the opportunity to receive the psychedelic intervention after the primary endpoint assessment, to reduce the potential nocebo effect in control groups.²⁶

A connected methodological challenge is the concern for blinding. This is a core component of clinical trial design, ensuring that outcome reporting remains unbiased with respect to treatment allocation, preserving the validity and reliability of study results. Standard approaches to minimise bias typically involve randomisation, blinding of both patients and clinicians, and the inclusion of one or more control groups, often using an inert placebo.²⁷ Psychedelic interventions present unique challenges to this process. The pronounced psychoactive effects of these substances make it difficult to conceal treatment allocation from either participants or investigators, while the limited understanding of their mechanisms of action and an informed participant population further complicate study design.²⁸ Researchers have used a range of strategies to address these challenges and maintain blinding, such as the use of active placebos

²⁵ Gisby M, Wolswijk F (2025). *Reimbursement Pathways for Psychedelic Therapies in Europe*. Magnetar Access and Blossom.

²⁶ Mertens LJ, Koslowski M, Betzeler F, Evens R, Gulles M, Jungaberle A, et al. (2022). *Methodological challenges in psychedelic drug trials: Efficacy and safety of psilocybin in treatment-resistant major depression (EPIsoDE) – Rationale and study design*. *Neuroscience Applied*, 1(100104).

²⁷ Rucker JJH, Iliff J, Nutt DJ (2018). *Psychiatry & the Psychedelic Drugs. Past, Present & Future*. *Neuropharmacology*, 142, 200–218.

²⁸ Destoop M, Mohr P, Butlen-Ducuing F, Kéri P, Samochowiec J, De Picker L, Fiorillo A, Kuypers KPC, Dom G (2025). *Use of psychedelic treatments in psychiatric clinical practice: an EPA policy paper*. *European Psychiatry*, 68(1), 1–7.

that induce physiological effects, such as niacin,²⁹ methylphenidate,³⁰ or the psychedelic at a low dose.³¹

The influence of expectancy effects extends beyond pharmacological factors to the psychosocial dimension of psychedelic research. A participant's prior experience with psychedelics is an important enough factor that some studies have excluded experienced participants or set up separate cohorts to enable analysis.³² A participant's prior experience with psychotherapy and their individual psychological resources may similarly shape their experience during the treatment period and may be considered in patient screening and study analysis.³³ The therapeutic alliance between patient and practitioner, may also influence expectations and perceived outcomes.³⁴ Future research may seek to reduce risks of unblinding through the selection of psychedelic naïve participants and the use of control interventions involving psychoactive substances with minimal therapeutic potential.³⁵ Many of the methodological challenges identified in psychedelic research, including expectancy and blinding, are not unique to this field but reflect issues shared across psychopharmacology and psychotherapy research.³⁶

2.3 Psychosocial Aspects

Psychosocial factors can significantly influence patient-reported and recorded outcomes. Consequently, trial results may exhibit substantial variability due to the diverse elements involved in the preparation, supervision, and integration phases. While some protocols seek to standardise these components, differences in cultural and clinical contexts persist, raising important considerations regarding the reproducibility and generalisability of findings across sites, conditions, and populations. These psychosocial influences, including participant's mindset and the physical environment, are often captured under the term *set and setting*.³⁷

²⁹ Ross S, Bossis A, Guss J, Agin-Liebes G, Malone T, Cohen B, *et al.* (2016). [Rapid and sustained symptom reduction following psilocybin treatment for anxiety and depression in patients with life-threatening cancer: a randomized controlled trial.](#) *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, 30(12):1165–1180.

³⁰ Griffiths RR, Richards WA, McCann U, Jesse R. (2006) [Psilocybin can occasion mystical-type experiences having substantial and sustained personal meaning and spiritual significance.](#) *Psychopharmacology*, 187(3), 263–283.

³¹ Goodwin GM, Aaronson ST, Alvarez O, Arden PC, Baker A, Bennett JC, *et al.* (2022). [Single-dose psilocybin for a treatment-resistant episode of major depression.](#) *New England Journal of Medicine*, 387(18), 1637–1648.

³² Muthukumaraswamy SD, Forsyth A, Lumley T (2021). [Blinding and expectancy confounds in psychedelic randomized controlled trials.](#) *Expert Review of Clinical Pharmacology*, 14(9), 1133-1152.

³³ Viljoen G, Walter H, Bendau A, Koslowski M, Betzler F. [Predictors of therapeutic response to psychedelic-assisted therapy: A systematic review.](#) *Journal of Psychopharmacology*. 2025;0(0).

³⁴ Destoop M, Mohr P, Butten-Ducuing F, Kéri P, Samochowiec J, De Picker L, Fiorillo A, Kuypers KPC, Dom G (2025). [Use of psychedelic treatments in psychiatric clinical practice: an EPA policy paper.](#) *European Psychiatry*, 68(1), 1–7.

³⁵ McCulloch DE, Liechti ME, Kuypers KPC, Nutt D, Lundberg J, Siggaard Stenbæk D, *et al.* (2024). [Knowledge gaps in psychedelic medicalisation: Clinical studies and regulatory aspects.](#) *Neuroscience Applied*, 3(103938).

³⁶ Aday JS, Heifets BD, Pratscher SD, Bradley E, Raymond R, Woolley JD (2022). [Great Expectations: recommendations for improving the methodological rigor of psychedelic clinical trials.](#) *Psychopharmacology*, 239(6), 1989–2010.

³⁷ European Medicines Agency (2024). [EMA Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics: Workshop Report.](#)

Psychedelic Therapy

Psychedelic treatment is often conceived as including a component of psychological support or psychotherapy. In this case, psychological support is intended to prepare and inform the patient before the intervention, ensure patient safety during the psychedelic experience, and provide support afterwards with the integration of the experience. In contrast, psychotherapy introduces a more active, specific therapeutic intervention that may influence treatment efficacy and where the psychedelic effect is viewed as improving the effectiveness of the psychotherapeutic intervention.³⁸ These different approaches are not necessarily a consensus position. Some researchers argue that characterising the psychedelic treatments, at minimum, as pharmacological interventions with psychological support for safety is unnecessarily categorical and does not accurately reflect actual clinical practice.³⁹ For the purposes of this paper, the open term *psychedelic therapy* is used to encompass these varied approaches, without taking a position on the specific role or form of psychological intervention in contributing to safety and efficacy. The literature also employs related though not interchangeable terms such as *psychedelic treatment*, *psychedelic-assisted therapy*, *psychedelic-assisted psychotherapy*, and *pharmacologically assisted psychotherapy* and *psycholytic therapy*.

Psychedelic therapy is generally structured around a three-phase model consisting of preparation, treatment, and integration, with one or more sessions at each phase.⁴⁰ The preparation phase serves to inform participants about the process, build therapeutic rapport, and address expectations or concerns. This is followed by one or more inward-focused psychedelic sessions, after which integration sessions support reflection on the experience and facilitate potential cognitive and behavioural changes. A systematic review of clinical psychedelic research found that, while certain structural elements are consistent across studies, the therapeutic stance and theoretical frameworks remain only partially defined.⁴¹ Given that psychedelics appear to heighten sensitivity to internal and external cues, future studies should describe how therapeutic conditions are shaped in greater detail, through suggestions, framing of treatment expectations, chosen therapeutic models, and the quality of the therapeutic relationship.

The achievement of a comprehensive understanding, standardised protocols, and transparent records of these psychotherapeutic aspects is one priority. A systematic review of 45 studies revealed significant limitations in the reporting of psychological interventions within psychedelic treatments, impeding the understanding of their structure and content.⁴² While a modest improvement in reporting quality has been observed over time, even recent studies remain inadequate. This lack of transparency poses challenges for interpreting treatment effects, elucidating therapeutic mechanisms, and replicating findings. To address this, the same rigour

³⁸ McCulloch DE, Liechti ME, Kuypers KPC, Nutt D, Lundberg J, Siggaard Stenbæk D, et al. (2024). *Knowledge gaps in psychedelic medicalisation: Clinical studies and regulatory aspects*. *Neuroscience Applied*, 3(103938).

³⁹ Gründer G, Brand M, Mertens LJ, Jungaberle H, Kärtner L, Scharf DJ, Spangemacher M, Wolff M (2024). *Treatment with psychedelics is psychotherapy: beyond reductionism*. *Lancet Psychiatry*, 11(3), 231-236.

⁴⁰ Aday JS, Heifets BD, Pratscher SD, Bradley E, Raymond R, Woolley JD (2022). *Great Expectations: recommendations for improving the methodological rigor of psychedelic clinical trials*. *Psychopharmacology*, 239(6), 1989–2010.

⁴¹ Cavarra M, Falzone A, Ramaekers JG, Kuypers KPC, Mento C (2022). *Psychedelic-Assisted Psychotherapy – A Systematic Review of Associated Psychological Interventions*. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 13(887255).

⁴² Seybert C, Schimmers N, Silva L, Breeksema J, Veraart, Bessa BS (2025). *Quality of reporting on psychological interventions in psychedelic treatments: a systematic review*. *Lancet Psychiatry*, 12(1):54-66.

applied to publishing trial results should extend to documenting the psychotherapeutic components of treatments, including the development of standardised protocols and manuals, to ensure replicability and preserve patient safety and wellbeing.

The EMA has emphasised that the role of the clinician, whether providing support or psychotherapy, has substantial implications for trial design, protocol development, and eventual conditions of use. Where psychotherapy is integral to the treatment, it is critical to ascertain whether observed benefits stem from the psychedelic compound, the psychotherapeutic intervention, or their combined interaction. In such cases, a factorial trial design may be necessary to disentangle the contributions of each component to efficacy outcomes.⁴³ Researchers, regulators, and industry can benefit from continued exchanges on these questions and setting shared priorities for future research.

2.4 Research Priorities

In the interview series that informed this guidance paper, several additional areas of research were identified as particularly important for advancing the field and supporting the future implementation of psychedelic therapies in Europe. These priorities span considerations related to patient populations, the characteristics and optimisation of psychedelic compounds, and the integration of these treatments within broader pharmacological and psychotherapeutic care frameworks. Together, they reflect an evolving understanding of how psychedelic therapies may be safely, effectively, and sustainably incorporated into clinical practice. Integral topics on psychedelic ethics are discussed in Section 4, while issues relating to health economics are addressed in Section 5.

Patient Safety

Across the research community, there is agreement that patient safety must remain the foremost priority in psychedelic research. Identifying and protecting vulnerable individuals before recommending psychedelic therapy is essential, as not all patients are suitable candidates for such interventions. The available data does not indicate that classical serotonergic psychedelics show potential for addiction.⁴⁴ Yet, concerns persist regarding adverse events and psychological complications, especially in the long-term. The scarcity of qualitative studies on long-term effects makes it difficult to identify and prioritise contraindications. Suicidal ideation and behaviours are rare and balanced by findings of decreased suicidality following treatment.⁴⁵ Clinical trial populations often include patients with elevated baseline suicidality due to the severity and chronicity of their conditions. A systematic review found that many clinical trials excluded participants that show signs of suicidal ideation.⁴⁶

⁴³ Browne K, Bałkowiec-Iskra E, Elferink A, Haberkamp M, Straus S, Sepodes B, *et al.* (2025). [Applying the EU Regulatory Framework to Determine the Benefit–Risk Profile of Psychedelics](#). *ACS Pharmacology & Translational Science*, 8(8), 2830–2838.

⁴⁴ Rucker JJH, Iliff J, Nutt DJ (2018). [Psychiatry & the Psychedelic Drugs. Past, Present & Future](#). *Neuropharmacology*, 142, 200–218.

⁴⁵ Zeifman R, Yu D, Singhal N, Wang G, Nayak SM, Weissman CR (2022). [Decreases in Suicidality Following Psychedelic Therapy: A Meta-Analysis of Individual Patient Data Across Clinical Trials](#). *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, 83(2).

⁴⁶ Meshkat S, Malik T, Zeifman R, Swainson J, Zhang Y, Burbach L, *et al.* (2025). [Psychedelics and Suicide-Related Outcomes: A Systematic Review](#). *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 14(1416).

The EPA has emphasised that suicidality remains a serious psychiatric emergency, requiring careful monitoring and preparation on the part of clinicians.⁴⁷ This underscores the need to determine which patients are most at risk, to develop effective prevention strategies, and to ensure extended clinical follow-up. The EMA has further emphasised that both psychosis and suicidality should be treated as adverse events of special interest, calling for systematic recording, documentation, and evaluation of such occurrences in clinical trials.⁴⁸

Patient Populations

Research on psychedelic therapies tends to rely on evidence from relatively small-scale studies. The current guidance on the safety evaluation of new medicines intended for long-term treatment of non-life-threatening conditions recommends a total clinical trial population of approximately 1500 participants prior to approval.⁴⁹ The research community recognises the need for larger and longer trials to adequately characterise the safety of psychedelics, particularly regarding their use in specific patient populations and their long-term effects. Systematic assessments of the current evidence for some psychedelics and indications have been conducted. A recent article found 30 registered trials that involved more than 2000 patients for the therapeutic use of psilocybin for depression.⁵⁰ Selection bias and recruitment challenges further complicate the development of representative evidence. Persons with prior experience of non-medical use have been among the patient populations of certain trials. Patients and clinicians involved in studies should ideally reflect demographic diversity across society, including ethnicity, language, gender, and age. Insufficient representation may limit the generalisability of findings and contribute to existing inequities in access to and quality of mental healthcare.⁵¹

Patient Experiences

Although the importance of optimising set and setting for ensuring efficacy and safety is increasingly understood, patient experiences and perspectives on these factors remains understudied. A systematic review of 15 qualitative research articles found that despite heterogeneities in the psychedelic compound, mental health condition, treatment setting, and qualitative methodology, patients reported positive and comparable therapeutic experiences, including personal insights, altered self-perception, increased connectedness, transcendental

⁴⁷ Destoop M, Mohr P, Butlen-Ducuing F, Kéri P, Samochowiec J, De Picker L, Fiorillo A, Kuypers KPC, Dom G (2025). *Use of psychedelic treatments in psychiatric clinical practice: an EPA policy paper*. *European Psychiatry*, 68(1), 1–7.

⁴⁸ European Medicines Agency (2024). *EMA Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics: Workshop Report*.

⁴⁹ International Conference on Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Registration of Pharmaceuticals for Human Use (1994). ICH Harmonised Tripartite Guideline: The Extent of Population Exposure to Assess Clinical Safety for Drugs Intended for Long-Term Treatment of Non-Life-Threatening Conditions.

⁵⁰ Breeksema J, Niemeijer A, Krediet E, Karsten T, Kamphuis J, Vermetten E, *et al.* (2024). *Patient perspectives and experiences with psilocybin treatment for treatment-resistant depression: a qualitative study*. *Scientific Reports*, 14(2929).

⁵¹ Destoop M, Mohr P, Butlen-Ducuing F, Kéri P, Samochowiec J, De Picker L, Fiorillo A, Kuypers KPC, Dom G (2025). *Use of psychedelic treatments in psychiatric clinical practice: an EPA policy paper*. *European Psychiatry*, 68(1), 1–7.

experiences, and an expanded emotional spectrum.⁵² Patient perspectives are particularly important for understanding adverse events. The identification of such events presents unique challenges, as qualitative studies suggest that transient, psychologically challenging experiences may, in some cases, contribute positively to therapeutic outcomes. Systematic reviews found that while psychedelic treatments were generally well tolerated in clinical and research settings, there is significant heterogeneity in the quality and consistency of monitoring and reporting of adverse events.^{53,54} Across studies and disorders, the most frequently reported acute psychological adverse events were anxiety, transient paranoia, confusion, and psychological distress, while the most common acute physical adverse events were nausea and headaches. There is a need for consensus on standardised methods for the systematic collection, evaluation, and documentation of adverse events during the psychedelic experience.

Treatment Intensity

The therapeutic benefits of psychedelics are proposed to be tied to the intensity and character of the subjective experience, although the exact nature of this relationship remains to be understood. Current research suggests that neurobiological mechanisms, such as increased neuroplasticity and the temporary disruption of entrenched cognitive and emotional patterns, may contribute to sustained clinical improvement.⁵⁵ In contrast to most approved therapeutic agents, psychedelics are administered across a notably wide dosage spectrum, reflecting differing strategies to optimise both safety and efficacy. The tendency to use of higher doses in clinical studies underscores the importance of understanding the interaction between pharmacological and psychological components of treatment.⁵⁶ The optimal number of dosing sessions also remains uncertain. A systematic review of 11 studies found that both single-dose and two-dose psilocybin treatments significantly reduced depressive symptom severity, with two-dose regimens in some cases producing more pronounced and durable improvements.⁵⁷ These questions can also be relevant to research into low doses (microdosing). A review of existing findings indicates that both LSD at doses of 10–20 micrograms and psilocybin at doses below 1–3 milligrams can produce subtle positive effects on cognitive processes such as time perception, convergent and divergent thinking, and activity in brain regions associated with affective regulation as well as increased

⁵² Breeksema J, Niemeijer A, Krediet E, Vermetten E, Schoevers RA (2020). *Psychedelic Treatments for Psychiatric Disorders: A Systematic Review and Thematic Synthesis of Patient Experiences in Qualitative Studies*. *CNS Drugs*, 34(9), 925-946.

⁵³ Hinkle JT, Graziosi M, Nayak SM, Yaden DB (2018). *Adverse Events in Studies of Classic Psychedelics: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis*. *JAMA Psychiatry*. 81(12):1225-1235.

⁵⁴ Breeksema J, Kuin BW, Kamphuis J, van den Brink W, Vermetten E, Schoevers RA. (2022). *Adverse events in clinical treatments with serotonergic psychedelics and MDMA: A mixed-methods systematic review*. *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, 36(10), 1100-1117.

⁵⁵ Browne K, Bałkowiec-Iskra E, Elferink A, Haberkamp M, Straus S, Sepodes B, et al. (2025). *Applying the EU Regulatory Framework to Determine the Benefit-Risk Profile of Psychedelics*. *ACS Pharmacology & Translational Science*, 8(8), 2830–2838.

⁵⁶ Royal College of Psychiatrists (2025) College Position Statement PS02/25: *Psychedelic and related substances (PARS) for medical use (including pharmacologically assisted psychotherapy)*.

⁵⁷ Salvetti GS, Saccenti D, Moro AS, Lamanna J, Ferro M (2024). *Comparison between Single-Dose and Two-Dose Psilocybin Administration in the Treatment of Major Depression: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Current Clinical Trials*. *Brain Sciences*, 14(829).

anxiety and alternating patterns of depressive and euphoric mood.⁵⁸ The potential of microdosing for treating depression and cognitive improvement remains uncertain. A recent study of longitudinal effects of microdosing psilocybin in two randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trials conducted in semi-naturalistic settings found that microdosing did not significantly affect cognitive or emotional functioning.⁵⁹ Research on microdosing is also important from a methodological perspective, as small psychedelic doses can serve as active placebos in clinical trials.

Maintenance of Effect

There is currently limited evidence on how long therapeutic responses to psychedelic therapy persist and how this influences long-term outcomes. There is, therefore, a need to better characterise maintenance of effect, addressing a significant knowledge gap identified by researchers and regulators.⁶⁰ The maintenance of therapeutic effect might vary depending on the psychedelic compound, its formulation, and the route of administration. Researchers have cautioned against categorising serotonergic psychedelics as either long-acting, such as psilocybin and LSD, or short-acting, such as DMT, as these distinctions may mischaracterise the actual pharmacodynamic effect.⁶¹ For instance, when psilocybin is administered orally, its effects typically build to a peak after about an hour and last between four to six hours, whereas intravenous administration produces an almost immediate onset with effects that subside within an hour.⁶² Since placebo effects associated with psychedelics trials tend to be short-lived, sustained improvements over time may represent a meaningful way to distinguish between genuine treatment effects and transient expectancy responses.⁶³ In one trial involving cancer patients, psilocybin was associated with large and sustained reductions in depressive and anxiety symptoms, with approximately 80% of participants continuing to show clinically significant improvements after six months.⁶⁴

Concomitant Medicines

Recent research has also begun to investigate psychedelic therapies and their interactions in more complicated settings that are likely to arise in clinical care. A scoping review of 18 studies found that the concomitant use of antidepressants and classic psychedelics, particularly

⁵⁸ Kuypers KPC (2020). *The therapeutic potential of microdosing psychedelics in depression*. *Therapeutic Advances in Psychopharmacology*, 10, 1–15.

⁵⁹ Prochazkova L, Marschall J, Lippelt DP, Schon NR, Kuchař M, Hommel B (2026). *Cognitive and subjective effects of psilocybin microdosing: Results from two double-blind placebo-controlled longitudinal trials*. *Neuropharmacology*, 283:110722.

⁶⁰ McCulloch DE, Liechti ME, Kuypers KPC, Nutt D, Lundberg J, Siggaard Stenbæk D, et al. (2024). *Knowledge gaps in psychedelic medicalisation: Clinical studies and regulatory aspects*. *Neuroscience Applied*, 3(103938).

⁶¹ Nutt D, Erritzøe D, Schlag A, Luke D, Mash C, Hiroyuki U, et al. (2025). *A lexicon for psychedelic research and treatment*. *Drug Science, Policy and Law*, 11.

⁶² Carhartt-Harris R, Erritzøe D, Williams T, Stone JM, Reed LJ, Colasanti A, et al. (2012). *Neural correlates of the psychedelic state as determined by fMRI studies with psilocybin*. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 109(6), 2138–2143.

⁶³ European Medicines Agency (2024). *EMA Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics: Workshop Report*.

⁶⁴ Griffiths RR, Johnson MW, Carducci MA, Umbricht A, Richards WA, Richards BD, et al. (2016) *Psilocybin produces substantial and sustained decreases in depression and anxiety in patients with life-threatening cancer: A randomized double-blind trial*. *Journal of Psychopharmacology*. 30(12):1181-1197.

psilocybin, appears to be generally safe, with no increased risk of serotonin syndrome.⁶⁵ This finding is significant because it suggests that the recommendation to discontinue antidepressants during psychedelic trials may be unnecessary and could even hinder therapeutic efficacy, while also imposing substantial burdens on patients, including the risk of worsening depressive symptoms or suicidal ideation. Another systematic review examined interactions between psychedelics, specifically psilocybin and MDMA, and a range of psychiatric medicines, including adrenergic agents, antipsychotics, anxiolytics, mood stabilisers, psychostimulants, and antidepressants, in the treatment of depressive, anxiety, and substance use disorders.⁶⁶ This current of research is important because many psychiatric patients receive multiple psychotropic medications and understanding how these drugs interact is essential for designing safe and effective therapeutic protocols. This addresses some of the core challenges faced by psychedelic research.

Comparator Treatments

In the interview series that informs this paper, there was an apparent consensus around the need for comparisons between psychedelics and antidepressant to make the case for approval and gather evidence for regulatory pathways in certain countries in the EU. Researchers have observed that conventional antidepressant treatments generally require several weeks at a full therapeutic dose before producing measurable effects, whereas psychedelic compounds may induce noticeable changes more rapidly.⁶⁷ A double-blind, randomised controlled trial comparing psilocybin with the selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRI) escitalopram over a six-week period in patients with MDD found no statistically significant difference in overall antidepressant efficacy between the two treatments, although secondary measures tended to favour psilocybin.⁶⁸ In the absence of more evidence, researchers have turned to network meta-analyses to allow for comparisons. One such paper examined multiple psychedelics alongside escitalopram for depressive symptoms reported that high-dose psilocybin yielded superior responses compared with placebo groups from antidepressant trials, though the observed effect size remained modest.⁶⁹ These findings underscore the need for more rigorous comparative research to determine the relative benefits and limitations of psychedelic therapies, compared to established antidepressant treatments.

2.5 Research Ecosystem

Psychedelic research in Europe remains in an early phase, characterised by small-scale trials. Yet these are gradually expanding in scale, precision, and interdisciplinarity. The field is moving

⁶⁵ Tap SC, Thomas K, Páleníček T, Siggaard Stenbæk D, Oliveira-Maia AJ, van Dalen J, Schoevers R (2025). [Concomitant use of antidepressants and classic psychedelics: A scoping review](#). *Journal of Psychopharmacology*, 39(10), 1072-1088.

⁶⁶ Sarparast A, Thomas K, Benjamin M, Stauffer CS (2022). [Drug-drug interactions between psychiatric medications and MDMA or psilocybin: a systematic review](#). *Psychopharmacology*, 239(6), 1945-1976.

⁶⁷ European Medicines Agency (2024). [EMA Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics: Workshop Report](#).

⁶⁸ Carhartt-Harris R, Giribaldi B, Watts R, Baker-Jones M, Murphy-Beiner A, Murphy R, et al. (2021). [Trial of Psilocybin versus Escitalopram for Depression](#). *New England Journal of Medicine*, 384, 1402-1411.

⁶⁹ Hsu TW, Tsai CK, Kao YC, Thompson T, Carvalho A, Yang AF, et al. (2024) [Comparative oral monotherapy of psilocybin, lysergic acid diethylamide, 3,4-methylenedioxymethamphetamine, ayahuasca, and escitalopram for depressive symptoms: systematic review and Bayesian network meta-analysis](#). *BMJ*, 386 (078607).

toward a more mature stage of scientific inquiry, with increasing attention to methodological rigour, transparency, and reproducibility. Researchers consulted during the interview series for this paper noted that academic groups are now forming networks and partnerships that aim to harmonise research protocols, and promote data-sharing capable of supporting large-scale, cross-border collaboration. Researchers have published methodological guidance to standardise trial design and improve the quality of evidence generation, particularly in relation to psychotherapy protocols. At the same time, perspectives diverge on some issues, including the appropriateness of scientist involvement in advocacy, the prioritisation of specific research areas, and the best pathways to integrate psychedelics into healthcare systems. Across sectors, there is broad agreement that the sustainability of psychedelic science will depend on diverse funding sources, including from public, industry, and philanthropic sources that preserve scientific rigour.

3. Clinical Practice and Care Experiences

This section surveys the emerging landscape of psychedelic therapy across the EU, concentrating on the compounds that are currently in clinical use, ketamine and psilocybin. It outlines the concrete care settings in which these substances are administered, and the early outcomes that inform practice. Access and equity are discussed in the subsequent section. Building on this overview, this section then examines the training and certification requirements identified by experts, proposing a core competency framework that spans psychopharmacology, psychotherapy and the phenomenology of psychedelic experiences. Finally, it highlights the ethical challenges that accompany delivery in real-world settings, underscoring the need for robust safeguards as the field progresses.

3.1 Current Practices

The practical application of psychedelic therapies is increasingly shaped by real-world experience from diverse care settings, complementing insights gained from scientific research and non-medical use. As the field evolves, additional access pathways have emerged, such as national compassionate use programmes, independent clinics, and physician prescription. Each of these pathways present unique positive and negative aspects. Together, they reflect a changing environment where clinical innovation, regulatory adaptation, and practical experience collectively inform the development of psychedelic therapies.

Clinical Research

Clinical trials and research programmes currently constitute the primary access pathway for psychedelic therapies.⁷⁰ These initiatives not only generate the evidence required for future regulatory approval but also contribute to the establishment of treatment protocols and the training of healthcare professionals. Across Europe, academic centres and research hospitals are conducting studies with a range of psychedelic compounds, gradually building specialised areas of expertise. In parallel, clinical research has facilitated the emergence of participant peer-support and advocacy networks, that have an important role in sharing experiences, promoting patient safety, and informing the development of best practices, such as the Psychedelic Participant Advocacy Network (PsyPAN).

Early Access Programmes

Early access programmes provide a regulated pathway for patients with severe conditions, where conventional treatments have proven ineffective and trial participation is not possible, to access unapproved treatments prior to full regulatory approval. Switzerland established a medical use framework in 2014, permitting the administration of MDMA and LSD for patients in palliative care or with PTSD, expanding access to psilocybin in 2021.⁷¹ There were approximately 80 private practices and 15 healthcare institutions that offered psychedelic therapy in 2024. Considering that patients are typically treated with ketamine 2 to 4 times, there were approximately 1660 treatments and 100 responsible physicians in the country that year. Norway authorised the

⁷⁰ Gisby M, Wolswijk F (2025). *Reimbursement Pathways for Psychedelic Therapies in Europe*. Magnetar Access and Blossom.

⁷¹ Liechti ME, Gasser P, Aicher HD, Mueller F, Hawrot T, Schmid Y (2025). *Implementing psychedelic-assisted therapy: History and characteristics of the Swiss limited medical use program*. *Neuroscience Applied*, 4(105525).

reimbursement of the off-label use of generic intravenous ketamine for treatment-resistant depression after a health technology assessment from the Norwegian Medical Products Agency (NOMA).⁷² Germany authorised a compassionate access programme for psilocybin in TRD was introduced in July 2025 under the Federal Institute for Drugs and Medical Devices (BfArM).^{73,74} Psilocybin therapy is provided at the Central Institute of Mental Health (CIMH) in Mannheim and the OVID Clinic in Berlin. This development follows extensive research in the country, such the Efficacy and Safety of Psilocybin in Treatment-Resistant Major Depression (EPIsoDE) trial.⁷⁵

Off-Label Use

Off-label use situations describe when a medicine has already received approval for one condition and is used to address another condition that patients experience. This can sometimes allow practitioners to treat more patients, whose conditions are not as severe, as in a compassionate use program. Certain countries permit physicians to prescribe approved medicines for off-label use or provide frameworks for pharmacy prepared formulations, such as in the Netherlands and Germany.⁷⁶ Given its off-label availability for mental health conditions, an increasing number of clinics and hospitals now administer ketamine for severe cases. These centres need to be equipped to administer it intravenously. An expert committee noted with concern that off-label treatment often proceeds without standardised training in psychedelic therapy, potentially compromising safety and therapeutic efficacy in the absence of appropriate psychotherapeutic support.⁷⁷ Such centres still provide an opportunity for practitioners to develop experience in delivering psychedelic therapies.

Independent Clinics

Independent clinics are in some cases early adopters of psychedelic treatments, particularly in the use of ketamine for mental health conditions. These facilities typically operate on a self-funded model, though some have developed agreements with private insurers or secured partial reimbursement for specific therapy components. Czechia has established clinical access to ketamine since 2020. The Psyon clinic in Prague and the Nové Elysium clinic in Brno provide ketamine-assisted psychotherapy for depressive, anxiety, addiction, and eating disorders. The centres have established partial reimbursement arrangements with the General Health Insurance Company (VZP), requiring patients to contribute a co-payment. To improve accessibility, the clinics also collaborate with philanthropic and funding organisations, such as Miton Psychonauts, to offer financial assistance programmes for patients with limited resources.

⁷² Psychedelic Access and Research European Alliance (2025). [Norway sets precedent on national reimbursement of generic ketamine for depression](#).

⁷³ Gründer G, Mertens LJ, Jungaberle A, Jungaberle H, Spangemacher M (2025). [Compassionate use of psilocybin for treatment-resistant depression in Germany](#). *Lancet Psychiatry*.

⁷⁴ Psychedelic Access and Research European Alliance (2025). [Compassionate use of psychedelic therapy approved for the first time in the EU](#).

⁷⁵ Mertens LJ, Koslowski M, Betzeler F, Evens R, Gulles M, Jungaberle A, et al. (2022). [Methodological challenges in psychedelic drug trials: Efficacy and safety of psilocybin in treatment-resistant major depression \(EPIsoDE\) – Rationale and study design](#). *Neuroscience Applied*, 1(100104).

⁷⁶ Gisby M, Wolswijk F (2025). [Reimbursement Pathways for Psychedelic Therapies in Europe](#). Magnetar Access and Blossom.

⁷⁷ Perez Rosal SR, La Torre JT, Birnkammer S, Chernoloz O, Williams M, Faber SC (2024). [Expert recommendations for Germany's integration of psychedelic-assisted therapy](#). *BMC Medical Education*, 24(1202).

Non-Medical Use

The non-medical use of psychedelics encompasses a wide range of practices, from longstanding ceremonial and spiritual traditions to contemporary forms of experiential and naturalistic use. Indigenous communities have for centuries incorporated psychedelics into their cultural and contemplative practices as part of broader systems of traditional knowledge.⁷⁸ Surveys indicate that most non-medical users take psychedelics infrequently, often seeking personal insight or emotional growth rather than recreational pleasure.⁷⁹ This diversity of motivations underscores the importance of harm reduction approaches aimed at minimising risk in non-medical settings such as retreats and in personal use.⁸⁰ Professional associations have expressed concern that delays in the clinical availability of psychedelic medicines, in conjunction with increased interest across society, may motivate some patients to seek access through illicit channels.⁸¹ The concern is particularly applicable for vulnerable patient groups, including persons with treatment resistant depression or severe post-traumatic stress disorder, who may enter into unregulated settings out of a lack of alternatives. In such cases, the absence of consistent screening, appropriate supervision, and continuity of care increases the likelihood of adverse outcomes for the patient.

3.2 Ethical Considerations

The ethical questions surrounding psychedelic therapy extend beyond science, encompassing patient safety, informed consent, adverse event reporting and the realities of non-medical use. Protecting participants demands rigorous, evidence-informed protocols that integrate pharmacology with psychotherapeutic expertise, while guaranteeing autonomy, transparent risk communication and systematic documentation of harms. At the same time, the growing prevalence of informal, culturally rooted or recreational consumption raises public-health questions that cannot be solved by clinicians alone. Consequently, ethicists, researchers, clinicians, patient advocacy groups, regulators and media must collaborate to devise shared standards, safeguard wellbeing and preserve trust as psychedelic treatments move toward mainstream care.

Patient Safety

Patient safety in psychedelic care raises distinct ethical considerations beyond those encountered in controlled research environments. The principle of *primum non nocere* (first do no harm) is essential, requiring that both pharmacological and psychotherapeutic aspects of treatment are delivered with an understanding of the biopsychosocial processes involved.⁸² Care professionals emphasise that pharmacologically assisted psychotherapy should align with evidence-based standards and established guidance for psychological therapies, ensuring that

⁷⁸ Urrutia J, Anderson BT, Belouin SJ, Berger A, Griffiths RR, Grob CS, *et al.* (2023). *Psychedelic Science, Contemplative Practices, and Indigenous and Other Traditional Knowledge Systems: Towards Integrative Community-Based Approaches in Global Health*. *Journal of Psychoactive Drugs*, 55(5), 523-538.

⁷⁹ Kruger DJ, Albrecht J, Aday JS, Barron J, Herberholz M, Boehnke KF (2025). *Tripping into Treatment: Comparing Initial and Current Motivations for Psychedelic Use*. *Journal of Psychoactive Drugs*, 1-7.

⁸⁰ Evans JMA, Aixalà M, Anderson BT, Brennan W, Bremner R, Brekke J, *et al.* (2025). *On Minimizing Risk and Harm in the Use of Psychedelics*. *Psychiatric Research and Clinical Practice*, 7(1), 4-8.

⁸¹ European Medicines Agency (2024). *EMA Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics: Workshop Report*.

⁸² Royal College of Psychiatrists (2025) College Position Statement PS02/25: *Psychedelic and related substances (PARS) for medical use (including pharmacologically assisted psychotherapy)*.

relational and contextual factors are appropriately managed. Standardised treatment protocols, patient autonomy, and professional oversight are viewed as essential safeguards against misconduct or unethical practices, particularly in emerging or independent clinics.^{83,84} This is especially important because patients in altered states of consciousness can be acutely vulnerable, with reduced capacity for making decisions in real-time and an increased dependence on the therapist, which can amplify power asymmetries and poses the risk of boundary violations. Patient advocacy groups and peer support organisations play an increasingly recognised role in promoting accountability, transparency, and shared learning within the field, reinforcing a culture of safety as psychedelic therapies move toward broader clinical implementation.

Informed Consent

Informed consent should include clear discussion of possible adverse events, such as symptom worsening, emotional distress, or unexpected cognitive or existential changes, while avoiding undue suggestion that might negatively influence the experience.⁸⁵ Clinicians have emphasised the need for structures to systematically record, assess, and report adverse events occurring during and after psychedelic experiences.⁸⁶ Accurate and transparent communication about potential benefits and risks, by researchers, clinicians, academic institutions, and the media, is essential to maintaining informed consent and public trust. Clinicians also emphasise the importance of mitigating contact transfer, where the therapist's own emotional state or distress may unintentionally affect the patient's response during treatment. Establishing complete, transparent, and available standards for documentation, communication, and emotional containment is therefore integral to safeguarding both patient wellbeing and therapeutic integrity. Clinical researchers have proposed solutions that address the challenges around informed consent in a comprehensive way, as in an article in *Nature Medicine*.⁸⁷

⁸³ Mustafa RA, McQueen B, Nikitin D, Nhan E, Zemplenyi A, DiStefano MJ, *et al.* (2024). *MDMA-Assisted Psychotherapy for Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder: Effectiveness and Value; Evidence Report*. Institute for Clinical and Economic Review.

⁸⁴ Multidisciplinary Association for Psychedelic Studies (2022). *Public Announcement of Ethical Violation by Former MAPS-Sponsored Investigators*.

⁸⁵ Evans JMA, Aixalà M, Anderson BT, Brennan W, Bremler R, Breeksema J, *et al.* (2025). *On Minimizing Risk and Harm in the Use of Psychedelics*. *Psychiatric Research and Clinical Practice*, 7(1), 4–8.

⁸⁶ European Medicines Agency (2024). *EMA Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics: Workshop Report*.

⁸⁷ Seybert C, Cotovio G, Madeira L, Ricou M, Pires AM, Oliveira-Maia AJ (2023). *Psychedelic treatments for mental health conditions pose challenges for informed consent*. *Nature Medicine*, 18(25).

Summary of ethical, regulatory and policy challenges and potential solutions	
Challenge	Solution
Altered state of consciousness during psychedelic experience, with consequences that are difficult to explain and anticipate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Obtain initial informed consent prior to administration of the psychoactive substance: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Full disclosure and detailed discussion of the potential effects of the psychedelic experience on autonomous decision-making and on possible wish to remove consent, and/or not to provide consent, if those effects had been anticipated; ▪ Full disclosure on potential need for rescue interventions, such as anti-psychotics for agitation, in the absence of added consent; ▪ Agreement on possible intervention techniques, such as touch and other grounding techniques, and the need for added consent. ▪ Application of intervention techniques during the psychedelic session, as per informed consent, and with added consent prior to their use.
Enhanced suggestibility and vulnerability in the psychedelic setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Initial informed consent procedures should include informing patients about the possibility of feeling closer or more familiar to clinicians, and potential impact on vulnerability to abuse. ▪ Professional oversight from regulatory agencies and professional associations.
Implementation of thorough procedures for informed consent outside clinical trials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Formal regulation and oversight of informed consent procedures from ethical authorities, regulatory agencies and professional associations
Definition of optimal clinical setting for psychedelic treatments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Favour hospital-based setting under standard medical supervision for the psychedelic session. ▪ Regulatory agencies and other authorities should consider other alternatives, such as a non-hospital setting, if equivalent safety and improved efficacy is clearly demonstrated.
Definition of optimal therapeutic procedures for psychedelic treatments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Apply treatments during psychedelic session as per procedures with best available evidence to date. ▪ Regulatory agencies and other authorities should define and regulate therapeutic procedures for psychedelic treatments and should support safety and efficacy assessment of specific procedures, such as psychotherapy. ▪ Professional associations for psychiatry, clinical psychology and nursing should provide joint professional regulation with specific technical guidance, training, certification, supervision and oversight.

Source: Seybert *et al.* (2023)⁸⁸

⁸⁸ Seybert C, Cotovio G, Madeira L, Ricou M, Pires AM, Oliveira-Maia AJ (2023). Psychedelic treatments for mental health conditions pose challenges for informed consent. *Nature Medicine*, 18(25).

Access, Equity, and Inclusion

The interview series that informs this paper found significant differences among stakeholders in the psychedelics space. These include the reasons for interest, conceptions of psychedelic therapy, and perspectives on its potential future implementation. One consistent area of similarity was an understanding of patient access, equity, and inclusion as an important ethical issue. Stakeholders emphasised that, once developed as safe and effective treatments, psychedelics could alleviate the profound personal and societal burden of mental health conditions. At that stage, ensuring equitable access may become the most pressing challenge. Stakeholders noted that treated patient populations in countries with early access remain small while funding structures remain reliant on philanthropy and industry to support clinical trials and cross-sector initiatives. The scarcity of public funding, standardised training, and a coordinated workforce was seen as contributing to uneven availability at present, which could contribute to inequities in the future. These would affect economically or socially marginalised groups. Interviewees stressed that inclusive policies, involving patient groups, civil society organisations, and professional associations, are essential to ensure that access frameworks reflect the safety and treatment needs of future patients through existing clinical professional structures. Many also cautioned that the commercialisation of psychedelic therapies could deepen inequities if affordability and public health priorities are not addressed through healthcare systems integration, reimbursement coverage, and transparent exchanges between regulators, payers, and industry.

3.3 Practical Considerations

The Royal College of Psychiatrists has published a guidance paper that advises clinicians on good practices for *set and setting* in psychedelic therapy.⁸⁹ It proposes that a multidisciplinary team of health professionals provide the intervention, given its clinical, psychological, and ethical aspects. The prescription for mental health conditions already demands specialist expertise in assessing treatment response, managing pharmacological interactions, and mitigating adverse effects. Psychedelic compounds add further considerations, including the need to understand altered states of consciousness, patient vulnerability, and transient physiological effects, such as cardiovascular effects.⁹⁰ A multidisciplinary approach is considered best practice, with psychiatrists, psychologists, and nursing staff with training in psychopharmacology and psychotherapy taking on complementary responsibilities throughout the process.⁹¹ In some cases, non-medical carers such as facilitators or spiritual guides may be included to support the therapy within standardised protocols, though always with the presence and supervision of medical staff.⁹² In every case, the effective provision of psychedelic therapy rests on the collaboration among carers, the adherence to standards of medical care, and the prioritisation of the patient's safety and autonomy.

⁸⁹ Royal College of Psychiatrists (2025) *Psychotherapy assisted by psychedelic and related substances (PARS): Guidelines for psychiatrists taking part in approved research trials*.

⁹⁰ European Medicines Agency (2024). *EMA Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics: Workshop Report*.

⁹¹ Grupo de Trabalho Multidisciplinar e Multiprofissional (2024). *Recomendações do Grupo de Trabalho Multidisciplinar e Multiprofissional sobre o Uso Clínico de Substâncias Psicadélicas*.

⁹² Poppe C, Villiger D, Repantis D, Trachsel M (2025). *Mitigating Ethical Issues in Training for Psychedelic Therapy*. *Neuroethics*, 18(25).

Training and Certification

Clinical trials and research programmes currently represent the main access points for psychedelic therapies in Europe, and they play a crucial role not only in generating evidence for regulatory approval but also in building clinical capacity. Through these studies, researchers and clinicians develop treatment protocols, refine therapeutic models, and acquire hands-on experience with the administration of psychedelics in controlled settings. Major academic and medical centres are emerging as focal points of expertise, offering an initial foundation for the future training of healthcare professionals. Private clinics have also contributed to this process by experimenting with delivery models under national regulations. Together, these efforts are shaping the early landscape of practitioner education and professional standards in psychedelic care. Professional associations and civil society organisations have proposed frameworks for training and certification, though formal curricula remain at an early stage.⁹³ Experts recommend establishing a clearly defined set of competencies encompassing psychopharmacology, psychotherapy, and the phenomenology of psychedelic experiences. Regular supervision by qualified clinicians and structured review of session documentation are seen as essential to ensuring safe practice. There is a general interest in expanding education, recruiting faculty expertise, and developing training manuals in psychiatry residency training.⁹⁴

⁹³ Royal College of Psychiatrists (2025) College Position Statement PS02/25: [Psychedelic and related substances \(PARS\) for medical use \(including pharmacologically assisted psychotherapy\)](#).

⁹⁴ Yaden ME, Ching THW, Goldway N, Roberts DE, Hokanson J, Gukasyan N, *et al.* (2024) [Psychedelic medicine in psychiatry residency training: a survey of psychiatric residency program directors](#). *International Review of Psychiatry*, 36(8), 902-907.

4. Regulatory Positions and Perspectives

Psychedelic therapies are raising increasing regulatory interest across the EU. The regulatory process rests on the decision of approval, which requires applicants to demonstrate the safety and efficacy of an innovative medicine through clinical trials. At the time of completion of the guidance paper in December 2025, no treatment involving a classical psychedelic has yet received authorisation in the EU. The advancement of clinical trials with compounds has, however, increasingly provided impetus for regulators to engage with researchers, developers, and civil society. Regulators have also commented on additional issues, such as the integration into existing ecosystems, the question on psychotherapeutic components, and the potential societal implications of their deployment. Since this paper cannot address the whole breadth of psychedelics research, these topics raised in interactions with regulators form the basis of the thematic scope of the analysis.

4.1 European Positions

There are several regulatory pathways of interest for psychedelic therapies in the EU. The European Medicines Agency (EMA) provides one centralised procedure for marketing authorisation for medicines, with a final decision from the European Commission (EC). Spravato (esketamine) is the only psychedelic-associated treatment to have received approval, specifically for treatment-resistant depression, in December 2019. The main alternative is for medicines to receive authorisation in one or more member states via their national medicines agencies. The EMA has shown interest in the therapeutic potential of psychedelics treatments and provided guidance to researchers and industry on the methodological challenges in clinical trials.

European Medicines Agency

The EMA Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics in April 2024 brought together regulators, researchers, clinicians, patient representatives, and industry stakeholders.⁹⁵ The workshop underscored that psychedelic medicines must follow the same overarching regulatory framework as all other medicines in the EU, while also acknowledging the distinctive challenges posed by expectancy effects, functional unblinding, and the integration of psychotherapeutic support. Participants highlighted the importance of early dialogue with regulators, methodological innovation in clinical trial design, and close coordination with health technology assessment (HTA) bodies to ensure that regulatory approvals are aligned with national reimbursement and implementation pathways.

The EMA started the process of formally incorporating psychedelics into its guidelines. The guideline on the clinical investigation of medicinal products in the treatment of depression was revised in September 2023 with the addition of a dedicated section on psychedelic substances.⁹⁶ The guideline, which was formally adopted in January 2025 and entered into force in September 2025, sets out baseline expectations for clinical development, recommending that programmes begin in populations with the highest unmet need, such as treatment-resistant depression, and demonstrate efficacy through randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trials, supported by

⁹⁵ European Medicines Agency (2024). *EMA Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics: Workshop Report*.

⁹⁶ European Medicines Agency (2025). *Guideline on clinical investigation of medicinal products in the treatment of depression*.

studies of maintenance of effect. The guideline highlights methodological challenges that distinguish psychedelic therapies from conventional antidepressants, including functional unblinding and expectancy effects, the need to characterise dose–response relationships while accounting for inter-individual variability, and the limited evidence base on durability of benefit. Safety is underscored as a core concern, encompassing psychiatric and cardiovascular risks, while the frequent integration of psychological support requires clear, standardised protocols to ensure that therapeutic effects are not confounded with those of psychotherapy alone.

The EMA has also found avenues to elaborate on its position, with officials contributing to papers to share regulatory perspectives with the research community.^{97,98,99,100,101} They provide practical recommendations for addressing methodological challenges, such as functional unblinding, through trial design. These include blinded or independent raters, verification of blinding through questionnaires, and comparison of effects through a range of doses. They further recommend clearer definitions of the patient population and the role of psychotherapy. For trials that feature psychotherapy, they propose a factorial design, as an option for determining whether therapeutic benefits are due to the psychedelic compound, the psychotherapeutic intervention, or any synergistic effect. The EMA recommends early and continuous engagement with regulatory agencies to align on these points. Researchers and industry representatives who participated in the interview series for this paper appreciated the increased clarity on regulatory frameworks and evidentiary standards, though translating their recommendations into reality will depend on factors such as available funding, future prospects, and national developments.

4.2 National Positions

The EMA regulatory approval of esketamine has opened separate national processes with assessor and payers.¹⁰² The Netherlands National Health Care Institute (ZiN) approved insurance coverage for esketamine in September 2021. Access remains complicated, the country's psychiatric, mental health, and depression patients associations raised concerns that only a fraction of the depression patients in the healthcare system would be eligible for treatment. The German Federal Joint Committee (G-BA) gave a positive assessment to esketamine for treatment-resistant patients in September 2023.¹⁰³ This ensures insurance coverage, though access remains

⁹⁷ Silva F, Butlen-Ducuing F, Guizzaro L, Balabanov P (2025) [A review of psychedelics trials completed in depression, informed by European regulatory perspectives](#). *Neuroscience Applied*, 4(105516).

⁹⁸ Browne K, Bałkowiec-Iskra E, Elferink A, Haberkamp M, Straus S, Sepodes B, *et al.* (2025). [Applying the EU Regulatory Framework to Determine the Benefit–Risk Profile of Psychedelics](#). *ACS Pharmacology & Translational Science*, 8(8), 2830–2838.

⁹⁹ McCulloch DE, Liechti ME, Kuypers KPC, Nutt D, Lundberg J, Siggaard Stenbæk D, *et al.* (2024). [Knowledge gaps in psychedelic medicalisation: Clinical studies and regulatory aspects](#). *Neuroscience Applied*, 3(103938).

¹⁰⁰ Butlen-Ducuing F, Silva F, Silva I, Balabanov P, Thirstrup S (2024). [Applying the EU regulatory framework for the clinical use of psychedelics](#). *Lancet Psychiatry*, 12(1), 7–9.

¹⁰¹ Butlen-Ducuing F, McCulloch, Haberkamp M, Mattila T, Bałkowiec-Iskra E, Aislaitner G, *et al.* (2023). [The therapeutic potential of psychedelics: the European regulatory perspective](#). *Lancet*, 401(10378), 714–716.

¹⁰² Gisby M, Wolswijk F (2025). [Reimbursement Pathways for Psychedelic Therapies in Europe](#). Magnetar Access and Blossom.

¹⁰³ Federal Joint Committee (2023). [Justification of the Resolution of the Federal Joint Committee \(G-BA\) on an Amendment of the Pharmaceuticals Directive](#).

restricted due to treatment costs and therapist capacity in authorised facilities.¹⁰⁴ The Czech State Institute for Drug Control (SÚKL) included esketamine among the medicinal products with public health insurance coverage in December 2024. This followed exceptional coverage arrangements and the negotiation of agreements with the country's major insurance coverage providers.¹⁰⁵ The Portuguese Authority for Medication (INFRAMED) authorised esketamine for treatment-resistant depression with full insurance coverage in May 2025.¹⁰⁶ In many of these cases the atypical psychedelic can or must be used in conjunction with an SSRI or SNRI. The Czech Parliament approved an amendment to the country's criminal code introducing the concept of the medical use of psilocybin, as separate to psilocybin as a scheduled psychotropic substance, so as to authorise its use as part of psychotherapy in healthcare settings from January 2026.¹⁰⁷

4.3 International Positions

EU regulators and national agencies have looked to precedents in other countries. The United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved esketamine in May 2019 and has since granted the breakthrough therapy status to the Multidisciplinary Association for Psychedelic Studies (MAPS) MDMA therapy for the treatment of post-traumatic stress disorder in 2017, Compass Pathways psilocybin therapy for treatment-resistant depression in 2018, Usona Institute psilocybin therapy for major depressive disorder in 2019.¹⁰⁸ The agency also granted the same status to several psychedelic analogues for depressive and anxiety disorders. The agency also published a new draft guidance on psychedelics in June 2023.¹⁰⁹ This contrasts with the EMA approach of integrating psychedelics into existing guidelines on treatment areas. The Australian Therapeutic Goods Administration (TGA) rescheduled psilocybin for TRD and MDMA for PTSD, authorising the psychedelics for medical use from July 2023.¹¹⁰ The country is the first to manage such a change of classification. The decision was met with praise from advocates while psychiatrists were unsure about the implications for patient safety and their capacity to prescribe psychedelic therapies in actual practice. Ukraine faces a considerable and unique challenge in addressing the mental health of its people, with an estimated 6.4 million persons experiencing severe, chronic post-traumatic stress disorder since the total Russian invasion on the country in February 2022.¹¹¹ The Ukrainian Ministry of Health has started the regulatory process to

¹⁰⁴ Perez Rosal SR, La Torre JT, Birnkammer S, Chernoloz O, Williams M, Faber SC (2024). *Expert recommendations for Germany's integration of psychedelic-assisted therapy*. *BMC Medical Education*, 24(1202).

¹⁰⁵ Gisby M, Wolswijk F (2025). *Reimbursement Pathways for Psychedelic Therapies in Europe*. Magnetar Access and Blossom.

¹⁰⁶ Facucho-Oliveira J, Esteves-Sousa D, Prates B, Neves R, Varandas P (2021). *Esketamine in Treatment Resistant Depression: The Way to Remission*. *Revista Portuguesa de Psiquiatria e Saúde Mental*, 7(1), 35–39.

¹⁰⁷ Dlestikova T (2025). The Legal Perspective on Psilocybin for Medical Use in Czechia: *A Key Milestone and the Case for Broader Consideration Beyond the Clinical Setting*. *Psychoactives*, 4(3) 34.

¹⁰⁸ Gisby M, Wolswijk F (2025). *Reimbursement Pathways for Psychedelic Therapies in Europe*. Magnetar Access and Blossom.

¹⁰⁹ Food and Drug Administration (2023). *Psychedelic Drugs: Considerations for Clinical Investigations Guidance for Industry*.

¹¹⁰ Therapeutic Goods Administration (2023) *Change to classification of psilocybin and MDMA to enable prescribing by authorised psychiatrists*.

¹¹¹ Marseille E, Chernoloz O, Orlov O (2025). *The Potential Economic and Public Health Impact of MDMA-Assisted Group Therapy for PTSD in Ukraine*. *World Medical & Health Policy*.

reschedule several psychedelic compounds for research and educational use while taking steps to raise the country's treatment capacity.

4.4 Political Influence

Political interest can sometimes influence regulatory developments. The Government of the Netherlands formed a State Commission on MDMA, consisting of experts from health law, addiction psychiatry, emergency medicine, drug prevention and criminology in April 2023. The group aimed to understand the recreational use, therapeutic potential, and health policy implications of MDMA. In its *Beyond Ecstasy* report, released in June 2024, the State Commission recognised the increased interest in using the compound among mental health patients with severe, concurrent, or treatment resistant conditions.¹¹² The report notes that while this is understandable, given the increasing scientific evidence, it is also a point of significant concern for patients who will access the atypical psychedelic in informal and illicit settings. The State Commission, therefore, recommended that the government provide patients with professional and accredited MDMA-assisted therapy. The report considered that the expected approval of MDMA in the US as a significant factor in raising patient interest in the EU. As the MAPS application has not passed at the time of completion of the guidance paper in December 2025, it is important to recall that psychedelics might enjoy a increase in interest after approval in one country, though such as regulatory process in any country remains complicated. Political pressure can also have a negative impact on approval. The Spanish Agency of Medicines and Medical Devices (AEMPS) accepted an early clinical trial into the safety and efficacy of MDMA-assisted therapy for the treatment of PTSD with the sponsorship of the MAPS in February 2000.¹¹³ The trial was stopped after political pressure on the main site after six patients had received treatment. The interview series that informs this paper found some stakeholders to be concerned about the uncertainty of political influence on future research and implementation.

4.5 Regulatory Priorities

Psychedelic therapies have encountered significant regulatory interest in recent years. In the interview series that informs this paper, some participants argued that the pace of change is sure to increase. EU and national regulatory agencies are, therefore, increasing their engagement with the scientific community and psychedelics industry. They emphasise that psychedelic therapies must follow the same standards and procedures applicable to potential medicines. Researchers, practitioners, and industry are encouraged to engage early and consistently medicines agencies and technology assessment bodies, to align on evidentiary requirements.¹¹⁴ This includes formal scientific advice processes as well as continuous dialogue through scientific journals and conferences. Clinical trials are expected to address persistent challenges in psychedelic research, such as unblinding and expectancy, while expanding patient cohorts, monitoring therapeutic effects over time, and including comparisons to existing treatments. The psychotherapy aspect within treatment protocols remains an open question, as national agencies differ in what they can accept and assess as evidence. Researchers have noted that

¹¹² State Commission on MDMA (2024). *MDMA: Beyond Ecstasy*.

¹¹³ Sessa B, Higbed L, Nutt D (2019). *A Review of 3,4-methylenedioxymethamphetamine (MDMA)-Assisted Psychotherapy*. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 10(138).

¹¹⁴ European Medicines Agency (2024). *EMA Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics: Workshop Report*.

national agencies may not be equipped to fully and adequately regulate the necessary associated procedures for psychedelic therapies, such as psychotherapy and enhanced informed consent, through instruments such as Risk Management Plan (RMP) and Risk Evaluation and Mitigation Strategy (REMS).¹¹⁵ The importance of health economic studies also varies by country. The experience of countries with pioneering regulators suggests that medical associations and civil society should develop clinical guidance and ethical standards to support safe implementation before treatments are authorised. Regulatory perspectives also adapt to legislative developments and monitor the international context.

¹¹⁵ Oliveira-Maia AJ, Seybert C. (2025). *Dilemmas in psychedelic medicine: From ethics to regulation and equity*. *European Neuropsychopharmacology*, 91:67-68.

5. Access, Implementation, Commercialisation

This section examines the questions surrounding how psychedelic therapies could be integrated into healthcare systems across the EU. It identifies recurring themes across discussions of access, implementation, and commercialisation, and introduces a framework for understanding potential access pathways based on three elements: authorisation, provision, and insurance coverage. The section also reviews the current routes of access outlined in earlier sections and proposes possible future pathways. Finally, it presents key insights from the interview series, including shared priorities and perspectives from industry stakeholders.

5.1 Systems Integration

The integration of psychedelic therapies into national healthcare systems is quite complicated, with significant variations already affecting access to innovative mental health treatments across the EU. Even approved medicines, such as esketamine, face uneven implementation, with many patients relying on independent clinics or personal payments. Health system integration represents one of the most resource intensive dimensions of implementation, given the number of national bodies involved in policy change.¹¹⁶ Psychedelic therapies typically require extended dosing sessions, specialised settings, and qualified professionals, a structure that needs adaptation from established institutions. Healthcare systems would need to adapt their physical infrastructure, establish certified training pathways for therapists and prescribers, and incorporate technological solutions for informing, monitoring, and contacting patients. Providers may not be able to invest sufficiently in facilities and training, without assurances that payment systems are in place. The experiences of integrating ketamine and esketamine have shown that technical, financial, and certification aspects can delay access even after regulatory approval. Addressing these issues early through coordinated planning and stakeholder dialogue will be crucial to ensure that future psychedelic therapies can be introduced safely, equitably, and sustainably into healthcare systems in the EU.

5.2 Implementation Themes

The potential future of psychedelic therapies in Europe depends on the alignment of several interrelated elements. A complete overview of these elements is not within the scope of this paper. Advice on implementation generally focuses on one or more substances, institutions, professions, or countries. The *Reimbursement Pathways for Psychedelic Therapies* report provides the most comprehensive analysis of the potential pathways available.¹¹⁷ Across the regulatory, implementation, and commercialisation pathways identified in the interview series, three themes consistently emerge. These are the authorisation, provision, and insurance coverage of the treatment.

Authorisation

Authorisation does not necessarily equal patient access. It is important to consider the conditions under which a psychedelic therapy may be administered, including the jurisdiction, eligible

¹¹⁶ McCulloch DE, Liechti ME, Kuypers KPC, Nutt D, Lundberg J, Siggaard Stenbæk D, *et al.* (2024). *Knowledge gaps in psychedelic medicalisation: Clinical studies and regulatory aspects*. *Neuroscience Applied*, 3(103938).

¹¹⁷ Gisby M, Wolswijk F (2025). *Reimbursement Pathways for Psychedelic Therapies in Europe*. Magnetar Access and Blossom.

patient populations, and approved clinical indications. This is seen in medical care settings with the psilocybin compassionate use programme in Germany and the ketamine medical use exemption in countries such as the Netherlands. Advocates for the implementation of psychedelic therapies in medical practice consider authorisation as a necessary step towards standard, conditional, innovative pathways. It is also important to acknowledge that informal and illicit use of psychedelic compounds is already happening and potentially increasing in any case.¹¹⁸

Provision

The provision of psychedelic therapies spans a spectrum of settings, from academic research centres and licensed healthcare facilities to independent clinics and informal or recreational environments, each presenting unique implications for patient access. This means that, even if they are authorised, patients who have the right and reason to use them may still find psychedelic therapies to be inaccessible. It is important to consider that some persons may still gain access to psychedelics even when there is no medical provision in their area, through international retreats and medical tourism in another country or informal and illicit use in the same country.

Insurance

The payment arrangements for psychedelic therapies introduce a further theme in categorising access pathways, with implications for sustainable and equitable treatment. These can include personal payments, private insurance, public reimbursement, or philanthropic support. The nature of the treatment significantly impacts cost. Swiss researchers estimate that the psychedelic itself may represent only 3% to 11.5% of the overall cost of treatment.¹¹⁹ When patients or philanthropy as payers are cited as a pathway, this usually assumes authorisation is granted and provision in private clinics. Advocates for the implementation of psychedelic therapies in medical practice generally aim for their integration into national reimbursement schemes.¹²⁰

5.3 Current Access Pathways

The current pathways for accessing psychedelic therapies were discussed in the previous sections on clinical care and regulatory positions. These pathways, from compassionate use to tropical retreats, can be categorised as either partial or informal, from the authorisation, provision, and insurance coverage framework used earlier. Compassionate use programmes and medical use exemptions provide narrowly defined routes for patients who have exhausted standard treatments. Indigenous and naturalistic practices continue to inform contemporary understandings of psychedelic therapy, while the growing recreational use of atypical psychedelics, such as ketamine from illicit sources, raises concerns for user safety. International connections are also evident, with the current state of retreat organisations and the potential

¹¹⁸ Marongiu S, van Eijk M, Gresnigt FMJ, Croes EA, Franssen EJF (2025). [Rising incidence of recreational ketamine use: Clinical cases and management in emergency settings](#). *Toxicology Reports*, 14:11940.

¹¹⁹ Liechti ME, Gasser P, Aicher HD, Mueller F, Hawrot T, Schmid Y (2025). [Implementing psychedelic-assisted therapy: History and characteristics of the Swiss limited medical use program](#). *Neuroscience Applied*, 4(105525).

¹²⁰ Gisby M, Wolswijk F (2025). [Reimbursement Pathways for Psychedelic Therapies in Europe](#). Magnetar Access and Blossom.

future of medical tourism reflecting rising public interest and uneven national approaches to psychedelic access.

Partial Pathways

The medical pathways currently available for patients in the EU can be described as partial, in that it does not feature a complete approach to authorisation, provision, and payment. This includes the off-label use for ketamine in many countries across Europe, the limited medical use programme for psilocybin in Germany, and the compassionate use programme for psychedelics in Switzerland. Participation in clinical trials can also be considered in this category. Patient access via partial pathways can still vary considerably. The Swiss programme requires regulatory approval for each patient, while the German programme allows licensed psychiatrists at the participating sites in Mannheim and Berlin to determine eligibility.¹²¹ Advocates of this approach have noted that this ensures medical and ethical standards while also achieving patient access without the additional burden of a complicated administrative process. Their main concern is that partial pathways are only open to a small share of the potential population. Swiss authorities granted less than 350 psilocybin authorisations in 2024.¹²² The German programme is meanwhile expected to start with no more than 100 patients in its first year from 2025.

Informal Pathways

Advocates for the medical use of psychedelics have raised concern that restricted access to approved treatments, complicated administrative processes, limited clinical capacity, and insufficient insurance coverage will contribute to the persistence of informal and illicit use across the EU. As public awareness of their therapeutic potential grows through media attention, demand increasingly outpaces the availability of regulated options. This dynamic could create a situation in which vulnerable individuals, particularly those with treatment resistant mental health conditions, may turn to unregulated or underground providers, often without appropriate safeguards.¹²³ A participant's choice of non-medical use does not necessarily reflect an absence of medical alternatives. Spiritual and naturalistic user and carer groups emphasise indigenous and community practices, advocating for their recognition and the importance of experiential forms of knowledge. This includes the communal, ritualistic use of ayahuasca as well as the professional, guided use of psilocybin sclerotia for therapeutic aims. At the same time, the recreational use of atypical psychedelics is also gaining attention. The safety and quality of intravenous forms of ketamine, authorised as an anaesthetic and prescribed to treat depression, is distinct from the powdered or crystal varieties available in recreational settings and imported illegally into the EU.¹²⁴ It is therefore important to distinguish between different forms of informal pathways when assessing their implications for public health and their interactions with medical

¹²¹ Palm G (2025). *Germany's Landmark Compassionate Use Program for Psilocybin: A New Wave for Psychedelic Medicine in Europe*. Open Foundation.

¹²² Liechti ME, Gasser P, Aicher HD, Mueller F, Hawrot T, Schmid Y (2025). *Implementing psychedelic-assisted therapy: History and characteristics of the Swiss limited medical use program*. *Neuroscience Applied*, 4(105525).

¹²³ Gisby M, Wolswijk F (2025). *Reimbursement Pathways for Psychedelic Therapies in Europe*. Magnetar Access and Blossom.

¹²⁴ Marongiu S, van Eijk M, Gresnigt FMJ, Croes EA, Franssen EJF (2025). *Rising incidence of recreational ketamine use: Clinical cases and management in emergency settings*. *Toxicology Reports*, 14:11940.

pathways. Informal pathways may also require policy engagement that proactively encourages its positive aspects for patient safety and affordable access.¹²⁵

International Access

Access to psychedelic therapies may be possible in another country when not authorised, provided, or payable in a patient's country. This could take the different forms. Informal centres sometimes engage in promotion to attract international clients. Clinical centres may also encounter medical tourism if the access pathways in the EU continue to remain uneven. There are some additional issues with international pathways. Psychedelic therapy protocols often require multiple preparatory, dosing, and integration sessions, increasing the logistical and financial cost of treatment. Additionally, patients may face language, cultural, or administrative barriers that could restrict access and affect treatment results. An optimistic view is that these international routes could place indirect pressure on EU and national regulators to harmonise standards and accelerate the implementation of complete pathways across the Union.¹²⁶ Pioneering countries could set precedents in safe, effective delivery models. International access will however only be feasible for patients with sufficient resources to get treated in another country. A potential increase in medical tourism is therefore generally not considered an acceptable scenario due to concerns for treatment quality, legal recourse, patient safety, and equitable access for the patient population in the providing country.

5.4 Potential Access Pathways

Advocates of the implementation of psychedelic therapy into mental healthcare have proposed additional pathways that could ensure authorisation, provision, and coverage as normative conditions. These usually include a standard pathway, which is recognised as complicated and, for some, not adapted to the methodological challenges or psychosocial components of psychedelic therapy. These stakeholders have therefore focused on conditional or innovative pathways as alternatives. The achievement of this sort of access to psychedelics would involve each of the elements presented in the previous sections, while also needing to adapt to each country in the EU.

Standard Pathways

Standard pathways envisage psychedelic therapies receiving marketing authorisation and passing a health technology assessment, starting the process to set pricing, insurance coverage, and reimbursement policies. This is particularly complicated since an EMA marketing authorisation is accepted in all EU member states plus Norway and Iceland, while HTA approval needs to be achieved in each country via separate procedures that may even involve more than one payer system.¹²⁷ Proponents of this approach look to the case of Spravato (esketamine), as the only psychedelic medicine to achieve centralised authorisation for a mental health

¹²⁵ Belouin SJ, Averill LA, Henningfield JE (2022) [Policy considerations that support equitable access to responsible, accountable, safe, and ethical uses of psychedelic medicines](#). *Neuropharmacology*, 15(219) 109214.

¹²⁶ Gisby M, Wolswijk F (2025). [Reimbursement Pathways for Psychedelic Therapies in Europe](#). Magnetar Access and Blossom.

¹²⁷ McCulloch DE, Liechti ME, Kuypers KPC, Nutt D, Lundberg J, Siggaard Stenbæk D, et al. (2024). [Knowledge gaps in psychedelic medicalisation: Clinical studies and regulatory aspects](#). *Neuroscience Applied*, 3(103938).

condition.¹²⁸ Their focus for the future is then, to address the methodological challenges and psychosocial questions around psychedelic therapies in clinical research while encouraging studies on health economics and financial support from industry. Countries, such as the Netherlands, that have more experience in evaluating innovative treatments, that have processes for considering the community cost and benefit of treatments, and that already provide insurance coverage for therapy sessions for mental health conditions, provide a more promising chance of psychedelic therapies using standard pathways.¹²⁹

Conditional Pathways

Conditional pathways may provide a more pragmatic route. The EMA has stated that medicines addressing unmet medical needs may be eligible for a conditional marketing authorisation, though this in itself would still entail the same health technology assessment challenges as a centralised marketing authorisation.¹³⁰ There is a time aspect to this route, as developers need to demonstrate the potential benefit to patients of immediate availability compared to the potential consequence of the time to pass standard procedure, such as conducting additional trials. It is unclear whether psychedelic therapies qualify for this approach. Advocates therefore propose that health authorities and policy professionals take additional steps such as evaluating psychedelic compounds plus psychotherapeutic components together, easing requirements for comparator trials with current treatments, and considering treatment benefits beyond clinical results, such as positive effects for patients, their communities, and the healthcare and insurance systems that support them.¹³¹ Since this pathway relies on legislators, regulators, and assessors adapting their processes, rather than industry and researchers meeting current standards, its success may rest on civil society advocating for psychedelics to be seen for their potential to address a mental health crisis.

Innovative Pathways

Innovative pathways represent an alternative, partially theoretical, potentially transformative approach to addressing psychedelics face with regulatory approval and systems integration. Innovation has already been discussed as a pathway for patients who participate in clinical trials to access treatment. In a similar spirit, industry actors are investing in adapting the psychedelic compounds themselves to preserve the neuroplasticity effects without the hallucinogenic properties, which are argued to be the main contributor to expectancy effects and a major reason for needing psychotherapy.¹³² The European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries (EFPIA) has increasingly referred to psychedelics as *psychoplastogens*.¹³³ Proponents of this approach argue that it is unclear whether psychedelic therapies may ever achieve the approval and assessment

¹²⁸ Browne K, Bałkowiec-Iskra E, Elferink A, Haberkamp M, Straus S, Sepodes B, *et al.* (2025). *Applying the EU Regulatory Framework to Determine the Benefit–Risk Profile of Psychedelics*. *ACS Pharmacology & Translational Science*, 8(8), 2830–2838.

¹²⁹ Gisby M, Wolswijk F (2025). *Reimbursement Pathways for Psychedelic Therapies in Europe*. Magnetar Access and Blossom.

¹³⁰ European Medicines Agency (2024). *EMA Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics: Workshop Report*.

¹³¹ Gisby M, Wolswijk F (2025). *Reimbursement Pathways for Psychedelic Therapies in Europe*. Magnetar Access and Blossom.

¹³² Psychedelic Alpha (2025).

¹³³ European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (2024). *2024 Pipeline Review – Innovation for Unmet Need*.

needed to achieve their promise for alleviating the burden of mental health conditions. Critics have argued that the psychoplastogens are still at too early a stage to present clear clinical effects,¹³⁴ and that subjective effects of psychedelics are necessary for their enduring therapeutic effects.¹³⁵

5.5 Commercial Environment

The commercial environment surrounding psychedelic therapies is evolving alongside scientific, clinical, and regulatory developments. Industry actors represent one of several stakeholder groups influencing their potential future integration into healthcare systems. The emergence of a *psychedelics sector* is increasingly studied through qualitative research¹³⁶ In addition to their contacts with researchers and regulators, industry actors also engage with consultancy firms, advocacy groups, and communicators in new ways. This emphasised their role in the broader discussions around access, implementation, and commercialisation, as well as its ethical and societal implications.

Industry Environment

The psychedelic sector features smaller specialised companies and established pharmaceutical corporations. These companies primarily focus on drug discovery and development, often centred on novel formulations, synthetic analogues, or innovative routes of administration.¹³⁷ Their activities also include manufacturing, clinical service provision, and the development of adjunct digital or therapeutic technologies. In contrast, larger pharmaceutical actors are more cautious, viewing psychedelics as a therapeutic class with uncertain regulatory and commercial prospects. The smaller psychedelic companies are increasingly pursuing partnerships with established pharmaceutical firms to secure the marketing, distribution, and sustainable investment required to translate clinical advances into accessible treatments within healthcare systems in the EU.

Industry Perspectives on the Future

In the stakeholder interviews that inform this guidance paper, industry representatives expressed diverse perspectives on the future of psychedelic therapies in Europe. The optimistic perspectives hoped that several compounds achieve EMA regulatory approval, with the support of EU funding for multi-site trials, standardised training curricula, and initial steps toward reimbursement within national health systems. The pessimistic perspectives envisaged a more fragmented landscape, marked by inconsistent national policies, high treatment costs, and scarce treatment capacity, factors that could slow clinical integration and restrict patient access. Industry stakeholders argued that responsible commercialisation also represents an ethical pathway to sustainable

¹³⁴ Aday JS, Barnett BS, Grossman D, Murnane KS, Nichols CD, Hendricks PS (2023). *Psychedelic Commercialization: A Wide-Spanning Overview of the Emerging Psychedelic Industry*. *Psychedelic Medicine*, 1(3), 150-165.

¹³⁵ Yaden DB, Griffiths RR (2021). *The Subjective Effects of Psychedelics Are Necessary for Their Enduring Therapeutic Effects*. *ACS Pharmacology & Translational Science*, 4, 568-572.

¹³⁶ Yoo M, Sakopoulos S (2024). *The Birth of the Psychedelic Industry: Capitalising on the Psychedelic Renaissance*. *Future Humanities*, 3(1) e70004.

¹³⁷ Aday JS, Barnett BS, Grossman D, Murnane KS, Nichols CD, Hendricks PS (2023). *Psychedelic Commercialization: A Wide-Spanning Overview of the Emerging Psychedelic Industry*. *Psychedelic Medicine*, 1(3) 150-165.

access. The development of psychedelic therapies is resource-intensive, and commercial investment provides incentives for quality research, manufacturing, and pharmacovigilance. At the same time, many interviewees from academic research and civil society raised the point that an overemphasis on pharmacological innovation risks minimising the psychotherapeutic component. They emphasised that industry involvement should extend beyond product development to include support for research into psychotherapeutic frameworks, patient experience, and systems of care, factors with a significant impact on whether psychedelic therapies achieve their therapeutic and societal potential. These findings are consistent with more comprehensive accounts of industry perspectives.¹³⁸

Industry Support to Research

Industry actors continue to have an important role in advancing psychedelic research, particularly in the development of new pharmacological treatments for mental health. In the current funding landscape, where public investment through EU or national research programmes remains scarce, much of the ongoing clinical work depends on a combination of philanthropic support, foundation grants, and industry sponsorship. Companies often serve as key intermediaries between scientific research and regulatory systems, possessing both the resources and the organisational capacity to engage directly with regulators, health technology assessment agencies, payers, and patient advocacy groups.¹³⁹ Industry stakeholders have raised concerns that EU researchers, funders, and patients may contribute significantly to global clinical development without gaining equitable access to resulting therapies. The case of Spravato (esketamine) illustrates the differences between the US and the EU, where its provision and payment via reimbursement remain limited and inconsistent despite regulatory approval and the support of Johnson & Johnson.¹⁴⁰

¹³⁸ Gisby M, Wolswijk F (2025). *Reimbursement Pathways for Psychedelic Therapies in Europe*. Magnetar Access and Blossom.

¹³⁹ European Medicines Agency (2024). *EMA Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics: Workshop Report*.

¹⁴⁰ Hardman J (2025). 'Beyond Guinea Pigs: Ensuring Access to Psychedelic Therapies for Europeans' in Gisby M, Wolswijk F (eds.) *Reimbursement Pathways for Psychedelic Therapies in Europe*. Magnetar Access and Blossom.

6. Civil Society Perspectives

This section relies primarily on insights from the interview series, complemented by stakeholder mapping conducted within the PsyPal project. It provides an overview of the civil society environment surrounding psychedelic therapies in the EU, encompassing European and national organisations that contribute to the development of the field. The section then discusses three important areas for civil society contribution to the potential future implementation of psychedelic therapies: the development of guidance from across sectors and stakeholder groups on topics such as care, research, and regulation; engagement in policy advice and advocacy with EU and national institutions; and the fostering of community through events, networks, and knowledge sharing among the stakeholders in the EU psychedelics space.

6.1 Civil Society Environment

Psychedelic therapies are the focus of an interconnected and evolving civil society environment. This includes European alliances, advocacy initiatives, patient associations, practitioner organisations, professional associations, philanthropic foundations, scientific councils, and national psychedelic societies. The resurgent interest in psychedelics is also apparent in this space, as many of the organisations cited in this part were founded within the last five years. A complete mapping of the civil society environment is not possible within the scope of this paper. The focus is instead on considering prominent or representative actors to understand the perspectives across the psychedelics ecosystem and the prospects for cross-sectoral guidance.

European Alliances

The Psychedelic Access and Research European Alliance (PAREA) is the organisation that best meets the criteria for a pan-European multi-stakeholder multi-disciplinary alliance for the psychedelics space. The organisation's governance is centred on its membership, consisting of European patient, practitioner, and professional organisations focused on psychedelics, mental health, brain health, neuroscience, chronic pain, and cancer. PAREA was founded in June 2022 and incorporated as a legal entity in December 2024. It is increasingly active in each of the four areas mentioned earlier. PAREA recently introduced a *community supporters* membership. This addresses an open question from the interview series on the best ways for civil society organisations to maintain smaller, effective governance structures while still achieving broader representation of the psychedelics space. It is particularly relevant for associations, societies, foundations, and advocacy groups that focus on a specific theme, country, or community within the wider ecosystem. PAREA also contributes to community initiatives, such as events, conferences, campaigns, and publications. It is also active as a catalyst and partner for EU research funding projects. PAREA also engages in advocacy with the EU institutions, forming the MEP Action Group on Psychedelics in Healthcare in May 2023.

Advocacy Initiatives

The civil society environment also features organisations that maintain a similarly broad EU-centred cross-sectoral focus while adopting a narrower mission with specific advocacy aims and organisational frameworks. PsychedeliCare was founded as a European Citizens Initiative (ECI) in January 2025. The initiative aims to gain signatures as part of this participatory democracy instrument to raise three advocacy appeals that the European Commission support the establishment of standards of psychedelic care, increase funding for research into the therapeutic applications of psychedelics to strengthen the evidence of their safety and efficacy,

and adopt a common EU position for international regulatory change and the potential rescheduling of psychedelic compounds at the UN. The volunteer-led initiative also contributes to building a European psychedelic community through its partnership structure, which united many national psychedelics societies and specific advocacy groups under one campaign for the first time. PsychedelicsEUROPE is another such advocacy organisation that consists of a core team of regulatory affairs professionals, an advisory group of medical researchers and funding from philanthropy. The organisation was founded in May 2021. Since then, it has contributed to international conferences and advised policy changes, such as the Czech amendment on the legalisation of psilocybin.¹⁴¹

Patients Associations

Patient associations have an important role in the psychedelic ecosystem by ensuring that the perspectives and experiences of patients inform research, clinical practice, and policy development. Clinical research projects are taking steps to encourage and enable the formation of patient support groups. Patient perspectives are essential for addressing some topics, such as access after the trial and support provisions¹⁴² Patient expertise is also integrated across multiple stages in mental health research and care through co-design approaches. The Psychedelic Participant Advocacy Network (PsyPAN) was founded as an organisation to connect psychedelic participants from clinical trials to treatment centres in July 2021. The organisation contributes patient inclusion in advisory initiatives on research practice such as the Reporting of Setting in Psychedelic Clinical Trials (ReSPCT) guidelines.¹⁴³ Patient groups nevertheless often operate with insufficient and unstable funding, facing significant informational and logistical challenges in uniting individuals across different countries and systems around shared priorities. A group that provided support circles for survivors of sexual misconduct or adverse experiences during psychedelic therapy or informal sessions managed to operate between September 2021 and October 2023. Patient groups in the psychedelic space could benefit from engagement with patients organisations such as the Global Alliance of Mental Illness Advocacy Networks Europe (GAMIAN-Europe) and the European Federation of Neurological Associations (EFNA). Partnerships between patients and professionals have can also be enhanced with the inclusion of associations that represent informal and family caregivers, such as the European Federation of Associations of Families of People with Mental Illness (EUFAMI).

Practitioner Organisations

The ecosystem also features organisations that provide medical and care practitioners with another avenue for engaging in events, research, training, funding, and advocacy apart from their primary centres for research or practice. These organisations may start with a national footing around a member community before developing an international presence. The OPEN Foundation is one such organisation, founded in the Netherlands in July 2007. It organises the biennial Interdisciplinary Conference on Psychedelic Research (ICPR) and provides the Advanced Education in Psychedelic Therapy (ADEPT) programme. The MIND Foundation is another such

¹⁴¹ Psychedelic Access and Research European Alliance (2025). [Czech Republic opens door to psychedelic therapy for mental health conditions](#).

¹⁴² Jacobs E, Murphy-Beiner A, Rouiller I, Nutt D, Spriggs MJ (2023). [When the Trial Ends: The Case for Post-Trial Provisions in Clinical Psychedelic Research](#). *Neuroethics*, 17(1):3.

¹⁴³ Pronovost-Morgan C, Greenway KT, Roseman L, *et al.* (2025). [An international Delphi consensus for reporting of setting in psychedelic clinical trials](#). *Nature Medicine*, 31, 2186–2195.

organisation, founded in Germany in November 2016. It provides the Augmented Psychotherapy Training (APT) programme. Practitioner organisations also support clinical trials and engage in advocacy settings. For instance, the MIND Foundation contributed to the successful compassionate use programme for psilocybin for treatment-resistant depression in Germany. The interview series that informs this paper found a general appreciation for practitioner organisations among stakeholders, though with the concern that insufficient funding and regulatory uncertainty may restrict their potential to provide education and training to enough professionals in the event that psychedelic therapies do receive regulatory approval in the future.

Professional associations

Professional associations from across psychiatry, psychology, neuroscience, and nursing have an important role in providing scientific fora and developing clinical guidance for psychedelics researchers. Since clinical trials represent such a critical component for the potential advancement of the psychedelic ecosystem, involving researchers, regulators, and industry actors, the methodological and ethical guidance professional associations can provide is particularly influential. At the same time, the promising evidence on the potential of psychedelic therapies to alleviate mental health conditions motivates these associations to support research and contribute expertise to the field. The European Psychiatric Association (EPA) published a policy paper on the use of psychedelic treatments in psychiatric clinical practice in its *European Psychiatry* journal in January 2025.¹⁴⁴ The association also featured a joint symposium on psychedelics with the PsyPal project as part of its European Congress of Psychiatry in April 2025. National psychiatric associations are also increasingly active in this area. The Netherlands Psychiatric Association (NVvP) released a memorandum on psychedelics in psychiatry in October 2024.¹⁴⁵ The Royal College of Psychiatrists recently published a position paper and an accompanying clinical guidance paper on the use of psychedelic and related substances (PARS) in clinical trials in September 2025.^{146,147} The European College of Neuropsychopharmacology (ECNP) has supported clinical research through its Psychedelic Research Network of centre representatives, organised their annual New Frontiers Meeting on psychedelics in March 2023, and published influential articles in its *European Neuropsychopharmacology* journal. The European Brain Council (EBC) has supported advocacy initiatives and organised policy events on psychedelic therapies in the treatment of neurological conditions. The European Association for Palliative Care (EAPC), European Federation of Psychologists' Associations (EFPA), European Academy of Neurology (EAN), Federation of European Neuroscience Societies (FENS) are also important professional associations to consider.

¹⁴⁴ Destoop M, Mohr P, Butlen-Ducuing F, Kéri P, Samochowiec J, De Picker L, Fiorillo A, Kuypers KPC, Dom G (2025). *Use of psychedelic treatments in psychiatric clinical practice: an EPA policy paper*. *European Psychiatry*, 68(1), 1–7.

¹⁴⁵ Nederlandse Vereniging voor Psychiatrie (2024). *Memorandum Psychedelica in de Psychiatrie: Handreiking voor de Therapeutische Toepassing van Psychedelica*.

¹⁴⁶ Royal College of Psychiatrists (2025) College Position Statement PS02/25: *Psychedelic and related substances (PARS) for medical use (including pharmacologically assisted psychotherapy)*.

¹⁴⁷ Royal College of Psychiatrists (2025) *Psychotherapy assisted by psychedelic and related substances (PARS): Guidelines for psychiatrists taking part in approved research trials*.

National Psychedelics Societies

National psychedelics societies are important actors in their countries while serving as first points of contact for medical professionals, practitioners, and advocates seeking to engage with the wider civil society space in Europe. These societies tend to consist of volunteers from the medical community though they also include members with therapeutic or legal experiences. Another contribution to the ecosystem is the translation of international guidance and advocacy resources into national contexts and languages. The Czech Psychedelics Society (CZEPS) formed an advisory group that informed the Czech amendment on the legalisation of psilocybin using guidance on regulating psychedelics.¹⁴⁸

Philanthropic Councils and Foundations

Philanthropic councils and foundations have an influential role in the psychedelic ecosystem by providing critical research funding while actively shaping and engaging with the broader ecosystem. Norrsken Mind (NM) is one such organisation that has supported scientific and policy community events as well as funding the *Reimbursement Pathways for Psychedelic Therapies* report.¹⁴⁹ Funders interviewed during this project emphasised the need for sustainable financing structures running over multiple years to sustain long-term scientific research and clinical translation into care. Many prioritise cross-disciplinary grants that integrate clinical, economic, and ethical perspectives to generate stronger implementation and health economic results. Foundations also advocate for combine academic, industry, and civil society expertise. Several have highlighted the importance of EU coordination initiatives and funding programmes, especially Horizon Europe, to harmonise research standards and ensure the sustainable development of the field across member states.

6.2 Advocacy and Communication

In the interview series that informs this paper, stakeholders cited advocacy as among the most important contributions of civil society organisations to the potential future implementation of psychedelic therapies. PAREA and the MEP Action Group on Psychedelics in Healthcare advocated for the organisation of the EMA Multi-Stakeholder Workshop on Psychedelics in April 2024. PsychedelicsEUROPE contributed to the turn to mental health policy since the Czech Presidency of the Council of the EU. PsychedeliCare has succeeded in uniting many civil society groups and national psychedelics societies around one consistent campaign. These initiatives have nevertheless faced significant challenges. Advocates noted that stigma against persons with mental health conditions and against the idea of psychedelic treatments continue to pose issues. Among the academics and clinicians interviewed, some shared that they did not engage with advocacy groups that appeared too activist, to protect the image of psychedelic use in scientific research and medical care, and its potential for patients, from more the stigma affected areas, such as non-medical use. Factors such as stigma can therefore impact the openness of different stakeholders to collaboration across the diverse environment, even around shared priorities. The interviews also encountered concern for the increase in enthusiasm and misinformation in social and new media platforms that often ignore the scientific evidence and misrepresents the potential benefits of psychedelic use, often without consideration for ethical questions or adverse

¹⁴⁸ Transform Drug Policy Foundation (2023). [How to Regulate Psychedelics: A Practical Guide](#).

¹⁴⁹ Gisby M, Wolswijk F (2025). *Reimbursement Pathways for Psychedelic Therapies in Europe*. Magnetar Access and Blossom.

effects. The interview series included persons who primarily contribute to the field as communicators. Initiatives to elevate the quality of public communication could become another priority area for civil society, in addition to policy advocacy.

6.4 Community Engagement

Civil society also contributes to a sense of community through events such as conferences, symposia, and meetings. These provide spaces for stakeholders to share perspectives and work together on shared priorities. Interviewees noted sustainable finances and inclusive participation as their main concerns for events in the space. The majority of events cited in interviews rely on participation fees to cover organisational costs. The interviewees mentioned that focusing on institutional, philanthropic, or industry support could come with positive and negative aspects. Alongside events, educational programmes and online groups have also fostered community. As with advocacy and communications, the success of community engagement through events also depends on identifying shared priorities that can unite diverse actors across the psychedelic ecosystem.

6.3 Guidance Initiatives

Advocates, researchers, and carers interviewed also emphasised the importance of associations stating their positions on psychedelic therapies and coming together across sectors and professions to provide guidance. This paper cites several such initiatives to align standards across essential areas, such as clinical care and scientific research. Some interviewees also recommended the development of guidance on additional topics that may gain in importance, such as support structures for trial participants, transparency standards for care protocols, and public communication that adheres to scientific evidence. The Champalimaud Foundation, Portuguese Medical Association (OM), Portuguese Psychologists Association (OPP), Portuguese Pharmacists Association (OF), and National Council of Ethics for Life Sciences (CNECV) initiated a multi-disciplinary and multi-professional group that produced a recommendations paper on psychedelic therapies, with a particular focus on providing actionable steps to ensuring patient safety and informed consent.¹⁵⁰

6.5 Civil Society Priorities

The interview series found a general consensus around several priorities for the future of psychedelic therapies among civil society actors, spanning research, care, ethics, community and coalitions. Interviewees emphasised the need to establish uniform professional standards and safety protocols, developed collaboratively with civil society, patient groups, and professional associations to address persistent methodological, psychotherapeutic, and ethical questions. Interviewees further emphasised the importance of expanding research interest and care guidance to the realities of personal experiences and non-medical use, as well as to the health economics and community impacts of psychedelic therapies compared to established treatments and the societal changes in mental health. Transparency in research, access to training, and coordination in advocacy were seen as essential to countering the fragmentation and stigmatisation of psychedelic practice. Interviewees raised the need for sustained funding and stakeholder collaboration across sectors and countries. These shared priorities can inform the formation of future coalitions and guide their mission, governance, membership, funding, and partnerships.

¹⁵⁰ Grupo de Trabalho Multidisciplinar e Multiprofissional (2024). [Recomendações do Grupo de Trabalho Multidisciplinar e Multiprofissional sobre o Uso Clínico de Substâncias Psicadélicas.](#)

7. A European Coalition

This section translates the insights gained through the interview series and presented in the sections on research, practice, regulation, access, and civil society into proposals for the formation of stakeholder coalitions to inform the potential future implementation of psychedelic therapies in the EU. The term coalition is used to refer to any European multi-stakeholder multi-disciplinary organisation that assumes psychedelic therapies as its primary focus. PAREA is therefore the main such a coalition at the time of completion of the guidance paper in December 2025. The proposals made in section are nevertheless applicable to organisations and initiatives that provide an inclusive forum for communities in the psychedelics space in Europe. Coalitions that adopt a formal purpose, priorities, membership, governance, resources, and funding structures to achieve their mission may miss out on consistent engagement with the rest of the multifaceted space. This section therefore proposes ways that coalitions can retain their strategies and structures while remaining accessible and responsive to the wider ecosystem.

7.1 Coalition Purpose

The choice of a purpose is a foundational step in the formation of any coalition. This aspect can determine the actors involved, the structure of their collaboration, and the change the coalition aims to achieve. Articulating their purpose can help a coalition position itself within the wider emerging and multifaceted psychedelics space. Sectors such as academic research, regulatory agencies, and the commercial industry have particularities in their ability to engage with partners across sectors. Actors such as medical associations, patient groups, and activist initiatives have unique perspectives on psychedelic therapies that need to be represented if they are to form a coalition together. National specificities are another consideration. The articulation of its vision and mission is therefore an important feature of forming and sustaining a coalition.

Vision

The vision states the coalition's shared enduring aspiration, the state of affairs that members intend to advance. The interview series found some common themes that could inform this. These include the recognition of mental health as a societal imperative, and the achievement of equitable access to psychedelic therapies as part of healthcare. PAREA also features these elements in its stated purpose. The general focus on psychedelic therapies can allow a coalition to remain agnostic to the questions on the right approach to the psychosocial aspects of the treatment. The specific focus on healthcare systems may not fit with some actors that advocate for informal, spiritual, and naturalistic forms of psychedelic therapy.

Mission

The mission translates this aspiration into actionable functions, such as core activities and the primary communities, of the coalition. A precise mission statement clarifies the coalition's everyday focus, making it easier for members, partners, and funders to understand its importance to them and allocate their resources accordingly. If a coalition defines its purpose narrowly, for instance around scientific consensus, it may attract a smaller, more specialised membership and have a technical focus. If it defines its purpose broadly, to include research, practice, regulation, industry and advocacy, it may achieve greater representativeness and yet face more complicated needs for coordination. The interview series found additional themes that that coalitions might consider when choosing their purpose, including the promotion of patient safety, the creation of

ethical standards, the development of professional guidance, the adherence to scientific evidence, and cooperation across sectors. Coalitions that identify such consensus points and put them in the foreground of their purpose may be better positioned to translate shared aspirations into real progress.

PAREA Mission:

We work to ensure the scientifically grounded, safe, equitable, and people-centred development and integration of psychedelic-assisted care into European health systems, making psychedelic therapies accessible and reimbursed.

Source: PAREA¹⁵¹

7.2 Coalition Priorities

Choosing clear priorities translates a coalition's vision and mission into actionable and measurable objectives that guide everyday activities. This part adapts the three important areas for civil society contribution to the potential future implementation of psychedelic therapies from the previous section and develops them as potential priorities of a coalition. These are not the only significant priorities, though a more complete analysis of the possible priorities of future coalitions would require further research into the psychedelics space in Europe.

Advocacy and Communication

The importance of advocacy and communication appears throughout the priorities of civil society organisations in the psychedelic space and will probably remain a primary focus of current and future coalitions as the field continues to emerge. Success may require a clear purpose, the involvement of experts, and the resources for continuous engagement. Advocacy activities can take various forms, reactive actions such as responding to public consultations or proactive initiatives such as organising campaigns and publishing papers. Potential targets include informing specific health policy proposals, countering stigma against mental health patients, changing perceptions of the use of psychedelics, sharing the scientific evidence on psychedelic therapies, and connecting their treatment potential to the concerning state of mental health in societies. PAREA released a policy paper in November 2025 that incorporates many of these elements to advocate for a more comprehensive policy package for mental health innovation from the EU institutions.¹⁵²

¹⁵¹ Psychedelic Access and Research European Alliance (2025).

¹⁵² Psychedelic Access and Research European Alliance (2025). *From Lagging to Leading: A Policy Toolkit for Mental Health Innovation "Made in Europe"*.

PAREA Priorities:

Developing an EU Mental Health Strategy. Without a strategy, mental health will remain everyone's priority but no one's plan.

Creating a European Mental Health Innovation Hub to coordinate expertise, infrastructure and collaboration across Member States.

Launching a European Mental Health Care Capacity Initiative to train professionals, expand treatment infrastructure, and integrate digital tools.

Piloting regulatory sandboxes for psychedelic therapies, enabling safe, early implementation under regulatory oversight while generating real-world evidence on safety, efficacy, and delivery models.

Source: PAREA¹⁵³

Community Engagement

Interviewees also considered coalitions as channels for community formation, engagement, and inclusion. This could be important for communities at an early stage of collaboration, that are too spread out to coordinate, or that do not have resources or face stigma. Patient and practitioner groups can therefore benefit from sharing experiences and practices. Coalitions might also support organisations that provide care or training through activities that foster community. Researchers can participate at scientific congresses and research conferences. Philanthropists could also benefit from such activities. Future initiatives could therefore aim to bring together groups that usually stay in separate spaces for community formation. PAREA and MIND Foundation are facilitating the creation of a European Funders Alliance for Mental Health Innovation.

Guidance Initiatives

Community engagement can also be a pillar for the third priority on developing guidance that was often raised in interviews as a potential priority for coalitions. In principle these initiatives might not require formal incorporated coalitions, though they would require the involvement of stakeholders across professions, sectors, and countries that is difficult to achieve without institutional support and resources. Guidance provision can be an aspect of many more specific targets, such as advice on clinical trials, care protocols, ethical standards, training programmes, regulatory frameworks, and access pathways. Advocacy can sometimes aim to strengthen communities, with appeals for public institutions to support guidance initiatives that researchers, practitioners, and patients are already invested in. This is the case for some of the three appeals of the PsychedeliCare initiative.

¹⁵³ Psychedelic Access and Research European Alliance (2025).

PsychedeliCare Priorities:

Creation of European standards: We want a group of professionals and patient representatives to come together and agree on standardised guidelines for the safe use of psychedelics in therapeutic treatments.

Increase of EU funding for research: We want the EU to boost funding for research on psychedelic therapies and to support the freedom to do such research.

Adoption of a unified stance internationally: We want EU member states to adopt a common stance on the legal classification of psychedelics on the international level.

Source: PsychedeliCare¹⁵⁴

7.3 Coalition Membership

A coalition that aims to gather perspectives from across the psychedelics space may include patient associations, medical associations, practitioner organisations, civil society organisations, philanthropic foundations, and national psychedelics societies as members. The space also includes academic institutions, research councils, pharmaceutical companies, regulatory agencies, healthcare assessors, insurance providers, public affairs professionals, consultants, and communicators. A plural membership can ensure that multiple perspectives and communities are reflected across the coalition's activities. This can however also introduce challenges for coordination, compliance with ethical standards, and equitable allocation of resources that need to be addressed in when shaping the coalition membership as a subset of the actors in the psychedelic space in Europe.

Civil Society Groups

One concern raised in the interview series affects the inclusion of civil society groups that gather important perspectives while not being incorporated organisations. These include academic circles, advisory groups, patient support groups, and many informal networks. Interviewees consistently emphasised that patient involvement is essential, pointing out that these groups often lack the resources to cover membership or participation fees. One option could be to organise advisory panels to involve patients and researchers. Another option could be for the coalition to remain unincorporated. PsychedeliCare adopted such an approach in its partnership structure. This allows it to give a European presence to national societies and community initiatives, such as harm reduction associations that provide support to recreational users of psychedelics. Coalitions can therefore position themselves to support national or community groups through representation and resources, such as guidance.

¹⁵⁴ PsychedeliCare (2025).

Commercial Interests

Certain categories of stakeholders may face restrictions on their ability to engage in an informal coalition with other stakeholders. One question raised in the interview series, is the inclusion of commercial interests in coalitions and initiatives. Pharmaceutical companies have a role in shaping the economic and access aspects of psychedelic therapies that is important to clinical research and regulatory processes. Public affairs professionals can accelerate engagement with EU institutions, national governments, regulatory agencies through familiarity with the sector and translation of evidence into policy messages. Communicators and influencers are also an important constituency in the space. The inclusion of these categories can present issues for academic researchers and regulatory agencies that must adhere to strong norms of conduct and policies for avoiding conflicts of interest. The EPA policy paper recommends that healthcare professionals be transparent and adhere to strict ethical standards when interacting with commercial entities.¹⁵⁵ Interests may also fluctuate over time across policy areas in some cases. It is important, for instance, that public affairs consultants and communicators involved in a coalition for psychedelic therapies commit to not engage in commercial activities that are contrary to the ethical principles and scientific evidence on public and mental health. Registration in the EU Transparency Register (EUTR) and compliance with professional codes of conduct, such as that of the European Public Affairs Consultancies Association (EPACA), are important though not sufficient guarantees. Coalitions may therefore need to adopt additional ethical and transparency standards or adapt their membership and governance structures if they aim to include commercial interests.

European and National Actors

European coalitions may miss out on involving national actors in the space. Yet, their perspectives and engagement is essential to certain priorities, such as achieving equitable access to psychedelic therapies in specific countries. Coalitions that function as structured organisations may choose to adopt a tiered membership model. These can include full membership with voting rights and accompanying commitments. They can also provide avenues for inclusion and participation through associate memberships, consultative statuses, or strategic partnerships, that can enable national societies, patient groups, academic centres, commercial interests, and prospective funders to engage with the coalition without the financial or administrative costs of membership. PAREA has introduced associate memberships and community supporters. This approach can also allow coalitions to maintain an EU vision while inviting associate participation from partners in countries such as Switzerland and Ukraine. A membership model, combining inclusivity with integrity, forms the foundation for a coalition that is capable of representing perspectives across communities, sectors, and countries.

¹⁵⁵ Destoop M, Mohr P, Butlen-Ducuing F, Kéri P, Samochowiec J, De Picker L, Fiorillo A, Kuypers KPC, Dom G (2025). *Use of psychedelic treatments in psychiatric clinical practice: an EPA policy paper*. *European Psychiatry*, 68(1), 1–7.

7.4 Coalition Governance

Governance is the set of structures and processes that determine the way a coalition defines its purpose, allocates responsibilities, manages resources, and remains accountable to its members, community, and principles. European coalitions in the psychedelic space need good governance because they bring together diverse stakeholders with different legal foundations, ethical standards, community perspectives, and strategic interests. Coalitions that align their governance structure closely with their vision and mission are more likely to ensure that strategic decisions reflect their intended purpose and that participation remains meaningful for its membership. Good governance is an evolving process. European alliances and associations often undertake periodic reviews of their own functioning and publish the results in their annual or impact reports. This supports transparency and continuous improvement while demonstrating accountability to members, communities, funders, and partners across the space. The specific design of governance structures and processes depends on a coalition's functions and formalisation.

Informal Collaboration

At one end of the formalisation spectrum, informal collaborations rely primarily on trust, shared interests, and voluntary cooperation rather than formal governance. Such coalitions can emerge organically in response to specific policy or advocacy opportunities. These can include joint meetings, statements, and initiatives. EU announcements and consultations can sometimes provide an impetus for civil society actors to form an informal coalition around an issue. Such arrangements can be inclusive, bringing together actors who may not have the mandate or resources to join formal coalitions. Their informality can however limit continuous cooperation, institutional memory, and access to funding. Informal coalitions can nevertheless be both a feature of a collaborative ecosystem and a stepping stone to more structured partnerships.

Anchored Initiatives

Some coalitions combine formal and informal features. A more formal incorporated organisation could serve as an anchor, providing a legal identity at a minimum, to events, groups, or initiatives that remain partially informal and autonomous. The anchoring organisation may also provide resources, such as a coordinating team or an online presence. This model can support both strategic governance and grassroots participation. Such structures are particularly suited to early stages of transnational and interdisciplinary collaboration. The PsychedeliCare initiative can be considered as a case study of this category, with its legal entity registered in Germany providing the governance and membership structure behind the European Citizens' Initiative (ECI) campaign of the same name.

Anchored Secretariat

Coalitions at either an early stage of governance formalisation or facing resources scarcity may function under the auspices of an established institution, such as a university centre or civil society organisation. This arrangement allows access to established governance systems without requiring immediate legal incorporation. The opportunity cost is the reduced independence, as the anchoring institution can retain some fiduciary responsibility and influence the coalition through aspects such as the resources it can allocate. For emerging coalitions, however, this format offers continuity without administrative costs while relationships and priorities are still forming. This is actually quite common in collaborations between civil society organisations and

Members of the European Parliament (MEP). For instance, PAREA provides the secretariat for the MEP Action Group on Psychedelics in Healthcare, EFNA provides the secretariat for the MEP Interest Group on Brain Health and Neurological Conditions, and GAMIAN-Europe and Mental Health Europe provide the joint secretariat for the EP Intergroup on Mental Health. MEP groups do not typically aspire to become formal organisations with governance structures and resources though.

Rotating Coordination

An intermediate governance form involves participative leadership among member organisations, typically with a rotating chair or coordinating body. This arrangement promotes shared ownership and prevents concentration of influence within one institution. Collective action can occur through periodic assemblies or steering committees. This also opens questions governance principles codification, steering committee composition, membership tiers, majority requirements, quorum requirements, mandate periods, accountability processes, and transparency rules. Such a format may benefit from the support of administrative staff or volunteers to document processes, manage finances, and preserve institutional memory. These elements may suit coalitions that need to sustain collaboration across specific professions, sectors, or countries over time without the need for full incorporation, such as an advisory council or guidance initiative.

Incorporated Association

Coalitions that rest on mature partnerships and commitments as well as significant financial and personnel resources may opt for formal legal incorporation. The coalition is usually a registered as a non-profit association, though legal statuses can vary across countries. Incorporation provides clarity over its governance processes and resource management, enabling the coalition to enter into contracts, apply for grants, and employ staff. It also requires statutory governance structures such as a governing committee and a general assembly. They are accompanied by internal rules concerning strategic actions, membership rights, mandatory audits, and codes of conduct. PAREA is representative of this category since its incorporation as a non-profit organisation registered in Estonia in December 2024.

7.5 Funding and Resources

A coalition's ability to achieve its mission depends on the way it secures and manages its resources. A safe financial foundation enables continuity of activities, participation across communities, sustained engagement in priority areas. Coalitions that define clear values around funding, such as integrity, consistency, sustainability, accountability, and transparency, are better equipped to maintain independence and meet members' expectations. The interview series found an emphasis on the importance of predictable multi-year funding, that allows coalitions to retain staff and focus on strategic actions that require long-term planning, such as guidance initiatives and international conferences. Transparent reporting on the origin and use of funds was also cited as reinforcing trust and showing integrity to the EU institutions, national agencies, potential partners, and funders.

The potential sources of funding available to a coalition may include EU projects, foundation grants, philanthropic funders, industry support, and membership fees or participation fees. Independence, transparency, and accountability are particularly important when receiving funds from commercial actors in coalitions consisting of or engaging with stakeholders with strict

conflict of interest norms and policies. Coalitions strengthen the European funding environment through conferences and platforms where philanthropic actors can exchange experiences and gain confidence in supporting research, advocacy, and community initiatives. Such efforts may help redress the current unevenness in international philanthropy, where most experienced funders are from and focus on the US. Some interviewees also recommended adopting a cross-sector multi-source funding approach to avoid dependence on any one funder and to support the coalition's independence in shaping its agenda.

Resources such as the knowledge, experience, and engagement of their personnel, volunteers, and members are essential to the coalition functions. Resources such as institutional trust, network access, and established partnerships across the space are among the most important assets. Effective resource management requires identifying these different forms of capital, aligning them with strategic priorities, and ensuring that their use reflects the coalition's values. The inclusion of communities in the mental health and psychedelic therapies spaces needs to be grounded in ethical treatment and genuine consideration of staff, volunteers, members, and partners, reflecting the same principles of care and wellbeing at the core of these communities. Resource management is therefore an important contributor to the capacity of a coalition to remain sustainable and achieve its mission.

8. Recommendations

This Section presents ten recommendations on the formation of multi-stakeholder multi-disciplinary coalitions that aim to shape the potential future implementation of psychedelic therapies in the EU. The recommendations are informed by the interview series, complemented by findings from published research, and the authors' knowledge of the evolving space. The earlier sections of this paper map the information gaps, unanswered questions, and sectoral priorities in research, practice, regulation, access, and civil society. This one does not provide technical answers to any one sector. It rather identifies features of a current or future coalition's mission, governance, funding, advocacy, guidance, policy, and principles that can ensure fruitful collaboration amongst the communities in the psychedelics space.

1

Coalition Formation

Actors from across research, practice, regulation, industry, and civil society, that are interested in the potential future implementation of psychedelic therapies in the EU are encouraged to form and sustain multi-stakeholder coalitions that provide a space for engagement across sectors, sharing experiences, coordinating advocacy, and achieving consensus.

2

Coalition Purpose

Coalitions are encouraged to embrace a purpose that recognises the societal importance of addressing mental health needs in the EU.

3

Ethics and Science

Coalitions are encouraged to embrace a vision on psychedelic therapy rooted in safety by prioritising patient experiences and scientific evidence.

4

Transparency, Completeness, Accessibility

Coalitions are encouraged to support researchers, practitioners, and industry in the provision of transparent, complete, and accessible guidelines on current practices.

5

Guidance, Standards, Protocols

Coalitions are encouraged to support the development and dissemination of guidance, standards, protocols, and training frameworks.

6

Policy Engagement

Coalitions are encouraged to facilitate contacts between researchers, patients, industry and civil society with regulators, legislators, and policy actors.

7

Access Pathways

Coalitions that advocate for access to psychedelic therapies are encouraged to adopt a broad approach, focused on established regulatory frameworks and standard access pathways as well as conditional and innovative approaches.

8

Encouraging Funding

Coalitions that advocate for sustainable funding are encouraged to initiate or support the creation of spaces for funders in the EU ecosystem.

9

Communication and Advocacy

Coalitions that include communicators and advocates are encouraged to ensure that communications remain rooted in the scientific evidence on psychedelics; with researchers, practitioners included or involved to provide advice.

10

Community and Governance

Coalitions that function with a formal governance and resources are encouraged to adopt and communicate a mission that represents their perspective and priorities, while finding ways to stay connected and create frameworks for cooperation that are representative of the wider community.

9. Conclusion

The PsyPal project, as the first multi-site clinical trial for psychedelic therapy funded by the EU, was established with the unique task of providing guidance to the emerging European psychedelics ecosystem. This guidance paper aims to inform the formation of sustainable, multi-stakeholder, and multi-disciplinary coalitions that can contribute to the potential future implementation of psychedelic therapies in the treatment of mental health conditions such as existential anxiety, substance use disorder, and depression, including treatment-resistant and major depressive disorder as well as post-traumatic stress disorder. It builds on the insights gathered through the interview series, published research, and the experiences of practitioners, researchers, and advocates across the EU.

As concern for the state of mental health continues to increase, a considerable population continues to experience chronic or treatment-resistant conditions that have an enormous impact on persons, communities, and societies. Psychedelic therapies offer promising evidence of safety and efficacy when delivered under controlled conditions and accompanied with appropriate psychological support. Yet despite this potential, the European ecosystem remains limited in its capacity to collaborate towards their integration into actual care. The space counts only one fully incorporated pan-European multi-sector coalition, the Psychedelic Access and Research European Alliance (PAREA), and one pan-European civil society initiative, PsychedeliCare. Given that these coalitions are still quite young, their success at integrating diverse and disparate perspectives around a shared project shows both the progress already made and the potential for collaboration across countries, sectors, and communities.

There is a chance to strengthen current coalitions and create new fora, initiatives, and spaces. Many critical questions remain unanswered, and significant information and cooperation gaps persist between national and sectoral actors. In scientific and clinical research, there is a need for institutional and financial support for large-scale, long-term clinical trials that can address the methodological challenges of psychedelic science, particularly around expectancy and unblinding, and the persistent questions about the role and form of psychotherapy. Academic researchers also require neutral and transparent platforms to engage effectively with regulators and industry partners.

In care practice, psychedelic therapy currently takes many forms, from some early medical or clinical programs to naturalistic and spiritual use. The priority remains ensuring patient safety, informed consent, and ethical care. Recognising the knowledge derived from informal settings is important. Illicit use of, primarily, atypical psychedelics remains a concern, underscoring the need for collaboration between researchers, healthcare professionals, and community practitioners to support evidence-informed public communication and progress towards safe, legal alternatives. Should psychedelic therapies receive authorisation, practitioner organisations that provide training and guidelines will have an essential role in supporting equitable access.

In the regulatory space, the EMA has become increasingly proactive. The challenge of coordinating national regulators, health technology assessors, and health insurance payers is complicated by considerable variation and uncertainty in their approaches to psychotherapy integration, health economics, and preferred pathways. The commercial environment also needs consideration. Innovation in psychedelic medicines development is strong; however, many developers are under-resourced compared to established pharmaceutical companies. Sustained collaboration between industry, researchers, regulators, and civil society advocates will be

needed to identify funding and collaboration approaches that build up industry capacity to work within standard pathways. The discussion of alternative innovative or conditional pathways, such as regulatory sandboxes, can complement this.

Civil society is an active and diverse segment of the ecosystem. It needs European coalitions to carry those perspectives into practical impact. The strengthening of coalitions, whether formal and structured, or informal and inclusive, will be essential to connect these communities, foster shared priorities, and enable coordinated advocacy, collaboration, and guidance. Coalitions will need to define their purpose and principles clearly, ensuring that governance, funding, and activities remain transparent and aligned with their values. As the ecosystem continues to emerge, coalitions that are governed and managed through embraced integrity, consistency, sustainability, accountability, and transparency may become a pillar to the stakeholder environment and its potential achievements in the future.

The responsible integration of psychedelic therapies in Europe will depend on collaboration and coordination among researchers, practitioners, regulators, industry, and civil society. The formation and sustainment of coalitions and initiatives including communities across sectors is an important step to ensuring that the standardisation and implementation of psychedelic therapies remain rooted in science and committed to providing safe, effective, and accessible treatment to persons in need of mental health care across Europe.

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Appendices

A. Stakeholder Consultation

The EPA conducted 21 online stakeholder interviews from July to September 2025 to gather inputs from across the EU psychedelic space and inform the preparation of the guidance paper. The invited interviewees were nominated through an anonymised and impartial process by PsyPal consortium partners.

The interviews were structured around three pillars, the participant's perspectives on the potential implementation of psychedelic therapies across scientific research, clinical practice, regulation, and access; their engagement with stakeholders across the space; and their priorities, interests, concerns, and advice for the future.

Participant agreement was the main priority for the consultation. The interviewers had the right to take notes and share findings on condition of anonymity. The interviewees had the right to review the notes for their session and recommend additional contacts and sources. The EPA has the right to retain the identified notes for the duration of the project while the consortium may retain anonymised notes for auditing purposes.

Accurate representation of stakeholder diversity was another priority. Interviewees were invited to describe their roles within the EU psychedelics space. The interviewers found that most participants could reasonably represent more than one stakeholder category, given their professional and personal experiences. Therefore, the authors established 12 categories and coded each interviewee as representing a minimum of one to a maximum of four of them. Each interviewee was weighted equally as 1 person.

Categorisation of interviewed stakeholders		
Categories	Stakeholders	Interviewees
C1	Academics & Researchers	5.5
C2	Clinicians & Healthcare Professionals	1.25
C3	Informal, Independent, & Spiritual Caregivers	1.25
C4	Patients, Participants, & Personal Experience	1.25
C5	Research Councils & Research Funders	2
C6	Policy & Legislative Institutions	0.25
C7	Education & Training Providers	0.25
C8	Healthcare Payers & Assessors	0.5
C9	Pharmacological Industry	0.75
C10	Journalists & Communicators	0.75
C11	Commercial Analysis & Consultancy	1.75
C12	Civil Society, Associations, & Advocacy	5.5

The stakeholder categories were far from equally represented among the interviewee cohort, with researchers and civil society actors together constituting a majority of interviewee perspectives. The researchers interviewed did represent a diverse set, with researcher perspectives included from psychiatry, psychology, neuroscience, qualitative research, economics, and law. Regulators and educators were particularly underrepresented. The nomination process included steps to increase the representativeness of the interviewee cohort in terms of nationality, gender, and age though these could not adjust for the stakeholder categories. The interviewees were based either in the EU or the UK.

Accurate analysis of the interview data was another priority. Among the set of interviewees, 5 were also consortium partners and therefore also contributors to the guidance paper. The authors took steps to avoid any conflicts of interest due to these dual roles. Consortium partners that contributed to the paper and participated in an interview were not engaged in the interpretation of interview results and did not edit any statements derived from interview findings.

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